

Dedication

I dedicate this work to my parents.

Their unwavering support and deep trust in my path made this entire course of study possible. The development I have undergone during this time of study will have a significant impact on my future life. Now, at the end of this chapter, I look back with great gratitude.

Thank you, Mom. Thank you, Dad.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my gratitude to everyone who contributed directly or indirectly to the successful completion of this bachelor's thesis.

My special thanks go to [REDACTED], who supported me in his own unique way as my supervisor. The weekly check-ins were an invaluable help in structuring the complexity of the topic. His encouraging message to be proud of my own work motivated me greatly.

I would also like to thank my three anonymous experts who took the time to participate in the exploratory interviews. Their in-depth insights into the practical world of AI implementation formed the empirical foundation of this thesis and played a key role in ensuring the practical applicability of the maturity model developed. I wish all interview partners all the best for the future.

Abstract

The implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) for process automation in the German service industry is essential. However, there is a high degree of organizational, technological, cultural, and legal complexity. This work addresses the existing research gap of a lack of industry- and application-specific control models. Using the Design Science Research (DSR) approach and conducting exploratory expert interviews, a practice-oriented maturity model is developed. The artifact is divided into five dimensions: Strategy & Governance, Data & Technology, Processes & Automation, Culture & Competencies, and Law & Ethics. There are five successive levels (Initial to Optimized) for each dimension, which are used to assess a company's AI maturity and to assign specific actions based on the assessment. The exemplary application of the case studies (FDSE AG, DigitalService GmbH) demonstrates the capabilities of the maturity model and its applicability to different scenarios. Companies can use the assessment and recommendations for action to create a roadmap for increasing their own AI maturity and thus ensuring long-term competitiveness.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), process automation, design science research (DSR), service sector, strategic management, empirical validation

Table of contents

Dedication.....	II
Acknowledgements.....	III
Abstract	IV
List of Figuren	VII
List of tables.....	VIII
List of abbreviations	IX
1 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Problem Statement and relevance of artificial intelligence	1
1.2 Significance of process automation through AI for value creation in companies	1
1.3 The German service sector as a key area investigation.....	2
1.4 Objective of the thesis and research question(s)	3
1.5 The Structure of the thesis.....	4
2 Theoretical Foundations	4
2.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Business Applications	4
2.2 Process Management and Intelligent Automation	7
2.3 Digital transformation and AI applications in the service industry	10
3 Challenges and success factors of AI implementation for process automation.....	12
3.1 Organisational Dimension.....	12
3.2 Technological dimension.....	13
3.3 Cultural dimension and employee acceptance.....	14
3.4 Legal and ethical aspects	16
3.5 Practical perspectives on implementation barriers: findings from exploratory interviews	17
4 Development of a maturity model for AI implementation for process automation in the German service industry.....	19
4.1 Theoretical foundations of maturity models and methodological approach to model development.....	19
4.1.1 Definition, purpose, and structure of maturity models	19
4.1.2 Analysis of existing maturity models in digitalization and AI implementation (with a focus on identified gaps)	20
4.1.3 Design science research as a research approach and model development process (including the role of interviews as input for the dimensions).....	23
4.2 Presentation of the maturity model	25
4.2.1 Vision and objectives of the model.....	25
4.2.2 Detailed description of the dimensions.....	26
4.2.3 Definition of maturity levels	28
4.2.4 Indicators and evaluation criteria for each maturity level and dimension	30
4.3 Recommendations for action regarding the transition between maturity levels	31
4.3.1 General recommendations for action for each maturity level.....	31

4.3.2	Specific recommendations for overcoming identified obstacles.....	32
5	Exemplary model evaluation and derivation of specific recommendations for action for service companies	35
5.1	Selection and description of exemplary use cases/companies.....	35
5.2	Performing the model evaluation for the selected examples	36
5.3	Derivation of specific recommendations for action based on the model evaluation	39
6	Reflection on the applicability and practicality of the model.....	40
6.1	Answering the research question(s).....	40
6.2	Scientific contribution of the work	42
6.3	Practical benefits and implications for the service industry	42
6.4	Limitations of the study and outlook for future research	42
	Bibliography	44
	Appendix with list	50
	Affidavit.....	53

List of Figuren

Figure 1: Spinning diagram of the maturity model (own representation).....	28
Figure 2: Evaluation of FDSE AG based on the model (own representation).....	37
Figure3: Evaluation of DigitalService GmbH based on the model (own representation).....	38

List of tables

Table 1: List of experts (own representation).....	17
Table 2: Indicators Table for assessing maturity (own representation).....	30
Table 3: Practical indicators Table for assessing current maturity (own representation).....	52

List of abbreviations

AG	Aktien Gesellschaft
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AlaaS	AI as a Service
BPA	business process automation
BPM	business process management
CMMI	Capability Maturity Model Integration
CoE	Center of Excellence
DL	Deep Learning
DMAM	Digital Maturity Assessment Model
DMMs	Digital Maturity Models
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DSR	Design Science Research
FAQs	frequently asked questions
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GenAI	Generative AI
GmbH	Gesellschaft mit beschränkter Haftung
HITL	human in the loop
HR	Human Resources
IPA	Intelligent Process Automation
iPaas	Integrated Platforms as a Service
KPIs	key performance indicators
LLMs	large language models
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLU	natural language understanding
RPA	<i>Robotic Process Automation</i>
SMEs	small and medium-sized enterprises
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

1 Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement and relevance of artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a transformative technology whose influence is not limited to technical aspects. It is establishing itself as a fundamental factor that is indispensable in today's business world. AI can be defined as a system that has the ability to understand external data, learn from it, and use this knowledge to achieve specific goals (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019, p. 1). AI is crucial because, together with global digital networking, it has the potential to fundamentally transform our growth, similar to the Industrial Revolution (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014, p. 67). Understanding the impact of AI on operating models, strategies, and competition is essential for all companies (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020, p. 62).

The rapid development and spread of AI is permeating all areas of life and the economy. The use of generative AI (ChatGPT or Midjourney) is currently revolutionizing the creative industry. At the same time, service and manufacturing companies are undergoing profound change (Fronczek et al., 2024, p. 212). AI-supported processes are also characterized by greater scalability and better integration with other digital systems, offering considerable potential for process optimization (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020, p. 64).

AI is considered a key technology for the future viability of companies and society. Despite existing fears, an increase in AI technology is foreseeable. Due to the expected productivity gains, competent use of AI is becoming a basic requirement for successful corporate management (Fronczek et al., 2024, p. 214). Therefore, it is necessary to thoroughly examine the implications of AI instead of just focusing on the media hype.

The integration of AI into existing corporate structures is a key challenge characterized by growing complexity. The disruptive potential of AI can cause anxiety among employees (Fronczek et al., 2024, p. 212). In addition, digital operating models harbor risks as well as opportunities, particularly with regard to data protection and social upheaval (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020, p. 66). In order to exploit the full potential of AI and manage the associated risks, systematic and strategic implementation is imperative.

1.2 Significance of process automation through AI for value creation in companies

Building on its general relevance, this section focuses on the application of AI in process automation. The implementation of AI in companies offers many advantages, including increased sales, cost reduction, and optimized business processes (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 1709). Nearly three-quarters of German companies use AI in process automation, but only half of them integrate it strategically (Heinrichs, 2024, p. 32). Companies with a higher level of digital maturity can use AI more efficiently, which can lead to a competitive advantage (ibid.).

AI process automation differs fundamentally from traditional methods such as robotic process automation (RPA). While RPA primarily automates manual, repetitive tasks via interfaces, it is gradually being expanded with AI functions (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 16). The expansion of RPA is known as intelligent process automation (IPA). It integrates various AI functions such as machine learning, natural language processing, and generative AI (Heinrichs, 2024, p. 34). Such AIs can perform complex cognitive tasks, such as evaluating data or classifying emails, which were previously too difficult for automation (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 1720). Taking over these tasks can lead to increased efficiency, productivity, and decision quality. One example of this is that half of finance teams spend ten hours a month manually reconciling data (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 14). In such cases, AI can take over repetitive tasks, allowing employees to focus on more challenging, creative work (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 89).

Automation through AI has a fundamental impact on value chains and can lead to the development of new business models. This makes it possible to offer customized products that automatically adapt to customer needs. To ensure the full potential of AI-supported automation, correct implementation is required. Heterogeneous applications and insufficient consultation complicate the process. The problem is solved by merging software and centralizing data on a uniform platform (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 13).

Other challenges include data quality, skills shortages, technical integration, and communication between managers and employees (Heinrichs, 2024, p. 35). Targeted employee training is particularly important to ensure internal competence (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 133).

In summary, intelligent process automation not only delivers efficiency gains, but also new competitive advantages and innovative business models. This highlights the strategic importance of AI for companies of all sizes and underscores the need to fully exploit its potential.

1.3 The German service sector as a key area investigation

This subchapter focuses on the connection between process automation and the German service sector. Currently, one in five (20%) German companies uses AI, and another third (37%) is evaluating its use (Hecker & Czachowski, 2024, p. 14). The use of AI is predicted to generate enormous value creation potential for the German economy, with expectations of up to €330 billion if 50% of companies adopt AI solutions (Bolwin et al., 2023, p. 5).

There is no universal definition for the German service sector because it is too heterogeneous. Nevertheless, two constant characteristics are often mentioned: immateriality and the integration of external factors. Immateriality refers to intangibility, meaning that it is not physically perceptible. The integration of external factors highlights the special role of customers. Both characteristics are therefore decisive in classifying an economic good as a service (Haller & Wissing, 2022, pp. 9–11). The digitization and automation of operational processes are central aspects of the German working world. The dynamic development of AI is forcing companies to take proactive action and engage with

this key technology, creating immense competitive pressure on the part of companies (Altenfelder et al., 2025, pp. 209–210).

There is a considerable need for AI-supported process automation in the German service industry. In the financial sector, the use of generative AI promises an enormous increase in productivity through knowledge and information processing (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 4). One example of this is DZ BANK AG's "dbTextract Shared Service." This generative AI-based tool supports document processing, reducing processing time by 40% (Wüst, 2025, p. 4). In addition, AI ensures that employees have efficient access to relevant knowledge when providing services and forecasts the demand for services (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 24). Signal Iduna, which uses an AI-supported assistance system for health insurance, was able to increase case closure rates in initial consultations by 20% (Wüst, 2025, p. 4).

Despite the great potential of AI implementation in the German service sector, there are specific challenges. Its introduction affects existing processes as well as knowledge generation and decision-making. This requires coordination between the IT department and the specialist departments; scalability, data quality, and system integration must be ensured, especially at the technological level. Organizationally, new competencies, processes, and governance structures are necessary (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 3). A major risk is that change management and employee acceptance will be neglected (Wüst, 2025, p. 4). Employees often reject new technologies because they fear losing their jobs to machines (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 77). Furthermore, AI can make mistakes, ranging from minor misunderstandings to serious errors that can seriously destroy customer trust (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 61).

Although the German service sector has great potential for AI-supported process automation, there are still major challenges that require a holistic approach. The technological, organizational, and strategic hurdles mentioned above show how complex the change is. This confirms the necessity of this work to support the German service sector in this change.

1.4 Objective of the thesis and research question(s)

The central research question of this bachelor thesis is:

- What dimensions and stages does a practice-oriented maturity model encompass that systematically controls the implementation of AI for process automation in the German service industry?

To answer the main research question, the following sub-questions are formulated:

- Research question 1: What organizational, technological, cultural, legal, and ethical challenges are dominant in the implementation of AI for process automation in the German service industry?

- Research question 2: How can the theoretical concepts of maturity models be transferred to AI implementation, and which dimensions and stages need to be taken into account?
- Research question 3: How can the developed maturity model be applied in an exemplary manner to assess the current status of a company and derive concrete recommendations for action for the next maturity stage?

1.5 The Structure of the thesis

This bachelor thesis deals with the topic of AI implementation for process automation in the German service industry.

The introduction (Chapter 1) introduces the relevance and problem definition, defines the research question, and explains the structure of the thesis. This is followed by the theoretical foundations (Chapter 2), which deal with AI in business applications, process management, and intelligent automation, as well as the transformation of the service industry.

Chapter 3 deals with the challenges and success factors of AI implementation, divided into technological, cultural, legal, and ethical aspects. At the end of this chapter, practical insights are drawn from exploratory expert interviews.

Based on the findings of the previous chapters, Chapter 4 develops a separate maturity model. It covers the theoretical foundations of a maturity model and the methodological approach. The maturity model is presented in detail, including its dimensions, maturity levels, and recommendations for action for the transformation to the next maturity level. In Chapter 5, the model is applied to a company as an example in order to present concrete recommendations for action.

Chapter 6 concludes with answers to the research question(s). In addition, the scientific and practical contribution is examined. Finally, an outlook for the future is provided.

2 Theoretical Foundations

2.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Business Applications

Artificial intelligence (AI) is not only about understanding AI, but also about building an intelligent machine that can calculate how to act effectively and safely in a new situation. Researchers have pursued different versions of AI over time. Some have defined the intelligence of AI as matching human capabilities, while others refer to this intelligence as rationality – “doing the right thing” (Russell, 2021, p. 19). There is therefore no general definition of AI. Basically, AI systems involve solving tasks that actually require human intelligence (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 23).

Although AI is also a major topic in the public sphere, this chapter focuses on its benefits in a business context. In this context, AI changes traditional processes by using algorithms and independently delivering added value (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020, p. 62). The industrial revolution relieved humans of

physical labor, whereas AI simulates, multiplies, and in some cases even substitutes our intellectual abilities. This results in new scaling and multiplication effects for companies and the economy (Gentsch, 2018, p. 3). It is clear that AI will shape our work in the coming years by optimizing decision-making processes and interactions (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 1).

The difference between AI and traditional programs is that expert systems do not have autonomous learning capabilities. AI, on the other hand, generates knowledge independently through neural networks and data-driven approaches (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019, p. 18). Some scientists emphasize that AI does not need to be explicitly programmed. Rather, it has the ability to autonomously perceive, interpret, learn, plan, understand, and act. Specifically, this means that AI receives data, analyzes it, derives knowledge from it, and can apply this knowledge to new situations, independently of predefined rules or sequences of actions (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 1712).

A key distinguishing feature is the difference between “weak AI” and “strong AI.” Weak AI has been developed for specific tasks, such as the production, distribution, and operation of physical goods, as exemplified by Amazon's warehouse robots or Waymo's self-driving cars (Google). Strong AI, on the other hand, is intended to replicate the entire range of human cognition (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020, p. 63). The majority of current applications involve weak AI, which is used for facial recognition and speech comprehension in virtual assistants.

Specific technologies are essential for generating knowledge from data and automating processes (Gentsch, 2018, p. 10). Five relevant technologies are presented below. A key technology in the field of AI is machine learning (ML). It enables machines to learn from data and improve their performance without manual programming. ML algorithms identify patterns in data in order to make predictions and enable the control of processes (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 5). The most common learning methods in ML include supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning, as well as reinforcement learning with human feedback (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 24).

Deep learning (DL) is considered a special area of machine learning. DL uses deep neural networks to recognize complex patterns in data sets (Gentsch, 2018, p. 25). It enables complex concepts to be grasped by processing information in increasingly abstract, hierarchically arranged concepts (Goodfellow et al., 2016, p. 23). DL is used particularly in image and speech recognition (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 28). A significant advance in DL is natural language processing (NLP), which is known for its expertise in the field of chatbots (Bartoletti et al., 2020, p. 7). This enables machines to understand, interpret, and respond to human language in text or speech form (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 21).

Generative AI (GenAI) and large language models (LLMs) are particularly important for process automation. GenAI uses DL and generates new content from an existing data set by replicating underlying patterns and structures (Shum, 2023, p. 1). What is special about this is that GenAI develops a model that enables it to develop content with similar characteristics (Schneider, 2024, p. 2). For this reason, GenAI can not only create text, but also images, sound, and videos (Shum, 2023, p. 2).

LLMs are a special type of GenKI. The significant difference is that LLMs focus heavily on text as opposed to other data (Wisbey1, n.d.). LLMs are trained on huge amounts of text, such as internet resources, reference books, and scientific publications. They attempt to generate human-like language from the data. When the AI is asked to generate a text, it calculates the probability and order of the words that appear. The largest LLMs are ChatGPT from OpenAI, Gemini from Google, and Llama from Meta AI (Busik, 2024, p. 744).

In summary, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) form the basis for AI systems and their ability to recognize complex patterns in data. Natural language processing (NLP) helps computers understand, interpret, and generate human language. Generative AI (GenAI) can use DL to create new content such as text, images, audio, and videos. Large language models (LLMs) are a special type of GenKI and can generate human-like text based on huge training datasets.

Despite growing interest and great potential, companies often face technical challenges. AI learns to make decisions based on the datasets used to train it. For this reason, the data that a company produces or has access to is of great importance (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 1715). Deep learning models in particular require a large amount of training data in order to learn effectively. In addition, the algorithms require computationally intensive and powerful hardware (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 34).

In addition, the data must be of good quality. If it is incomplete or flawed, this is reflected in the quality of the AI. Poor data quality leads to inferior and unreliable AI results (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 51). LLMs can suffer from data limitation, especially if the training data is only available up to a certain point. This can affect the correctness and precision of the generated responses (Shum, 2023, p. 217).

A worrying problem with generative AIs is that they sometimes generate factually incorrect but convincing responses. This problem is called “hallucination.” For example, ChatGPT generates fake court decisions, quotes, and internal references. OpenAI, the company behind ChatGPT, has acknowledged this problem and warns against completely trusting the AI with high-risk content (Shum, 2023, p. 218).

Ethical aspects are crucial as the boundaries between humans and machines become increasingly blurred. Companies must ensure that AI is developed on ethical principles and is free of bias. This bias in data and algorithms is a key problem (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 1719). Distorted training data used to train AI can lead to discriminatory results (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 119). For example, facial recognition systems do not work optimally for certain ethnicities, and language models reinforce gender stereotypes (Bartoletti et al., 2020, p. 7).

Another challenge is the black box problem and the lack of transparency. Unlike other programs, it is difficult to understand how AI makes its decisions (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 51). Another aspect concerns the fears of many customers regarding their privacy and the associated vulnerability to abuse (Gentsch, 2018, p. 70). AI systems require large amounts of data, which is usually sensitive, posing

significant data protection risks. It is crucial that data collection and use comply with GDPR standards (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 117). Furthermore, copyright and personal rights violations are significant factors that must be taken into account during implementation (Shum, 2023, p. 7).

A far-reaching social risk is the impact of AI on jobs. There is concern that AI will change almost every job and thus have a significant impact on the world of work (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020, p. 66). However, other experts see this differently: AI does not lead to the elimination of jobs, but rather of tasks that people perform in their jobs (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 87). Nevertheless, retraining and continuing education programs are of great importance in preparing the workforce for the changing requirements (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 4).

Another key aspect is regulation. In the EU, the GDPR must be complied with, in particular the EU AI Act. This aims to harmonize the regulation of AI systems based on their risk profile in order to ensure ethically acceptable and safe use (Shum, 2023, pp. 12–13).

In summary, it can be said that the integration of AI into business processes makes sense. This development is made possible by technologies such as machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), natural language processing (NLP), generative AI (GenAI), and large language models (LLMs). They are helping to usher in the next evolutionary step in process automation.

AI's ability to learn autonomously and apply this knowledge to new data sets is apart from traditional systems. Workflows are being transformed, and AI enables new economies of scale through its simulated intellectual capabilities. Despite technical, ethical, data protection, and social challenges, the implementation of AI is crucial for future competitiveness. It marks a transition from simple task automation to a comprehensive, data-driven transformation that accelerates processes and improves quality.

2.2 Process Management and Intelligent Automation

Building on a general understanding of artificial intelligence (AI), this chapter begins with the fundamental importance of business process management (BPM), which is considered a prerequisite for automation and digitization in companies. In this context, hyperautomation is defined as a business-oriented approach that combines various technologies such as AI, robotic process automation (RPA), and integrated platforms as a service (iPaas iPaaS). The goal is to optimize business processes by replacing human intervention (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1036). RPA enables companies to automate processes quickly, relieving employees of repetitive tasks. In practice, interfaces and ERP data in particular can be automated (Bulander et al., 2022, p. 45). The integration of AI opens up new opportunities for redesigning services and strategies, leading to a competitive advantage (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1036). AI is increasingly addressing administrative, scheduling, and planning processes in sales, marketing, and management in an effort to create a holistic “algorithmic enterprise” (Gentsch, 2018, p. 1). Consequently, business process management (BPM) is a foundation for any form of automation and digitalization in companies.

Business process management (BPM) is the discipline that provides approaches for designing, executing, controlling, measuring, and improving business processes (Aalst, 2016, p. 16). Business services are often highly complex due to the routine activities and tasks they involve. Performing these tasks can be stressful for people, resulting in inefficient work (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1037). Employees have to spend a considerable amount of their time dealing with processes such as quality monitoring or reporting. As a result, they are unable to focus on value-adding tasks, creative solutions, or valuable customer interactions. Furthermore, complications arise when different IT systems are used, leading to manual and error-prone tasks (Bulander et al., 2022, p. 46).

Process analysis is essential for identifying automation potential. Process mining is suitable for this purpose. It is a powerful tool and can bridge the gap between data science and process science (Aalst, 2016, p. 25). This is achieved by identifying new processes and through constant monitoring and improvement. In this way, knowledge is extracted from readily available results logs (Aalst, 2016, p. 31). It helps to uncover the discrepancy between planned (“de jure”) and actual (“de facto”) processes, thus facilitating the identification of optimization potential (Aalst, 2016, p. 303).

A robust database is essential for the success of AI. Only by centralizing data on a uniform platform can the automation routine run smoothly (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 13). It is also important to emphasize that owning data has no direct value if there are no algorithms to evaluate it and thus generate knowledge (Gentsch, 2018, p. 13).

Process automation is advantageous because it leads to increased scalability, accelerated processes, and a reduction in the need for manual work (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 14). Basic automation is typically achieved through robotic process automation (RPA) (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 16). RPA serves as a software automation tool that is used to automate repetitive tasks such as data extraction and processing (Gentsch, 2018, p. 47). It supports recurring, structured, and rule-based tasks. RPA works faster and more accurately than a human. Since it logs every transaction for quality assurance, it reduces the likelihood of errors and increases process quality (Bulaner et al., 2022, p. 47).

However, this also means that RPA has significant limitations, as it can only be used for rule-based applications. It lacks the ability to learn autonomously and think cognitively. This means that it is not capable of performing complex analyses or making independent decisions (Barenkamp & Schnier, 2023, p. 138).

The limitations of RPA have led to the development of intelligent automation through the integration of AI technology. Intelligent Process Automation (IPA) brings RPA and AI together to equip software robots with cognitive abilities (Barenkamp & Schnier, 2023, p. 138). Technologies such as natural language processing (NLP) and natural language understanding (NLU) are used to understand, evaluate, and process complex and unstructured data (human text and speech) (ibid.). IPA can learn with the help of these technologies and requires less human intervention because it can make

decisions independently (ibid.). By connecting with AI, RPA can counteract its limitation of “not being able to learn”.

AI serves as a catalyst for the transformation of business processes in today's digital age. It supports companies in creating real-time analyses and forecasts and enables improved customer understanding (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1037). Predictive analytics created by AI helps improve decision-making processes by analyzing huge amounts of data faster than human workers could (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1038).

The ability of AI systems to see, think, speak, and understand enables comprehensive business process automation (BPA) (Barenkamp & Schnier, 2023, p. 138). This results in hyperautomation, an approach that combines various technologies (AI, RPA, iPaaS) to reduce human intervention and make it more efficient (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1036).

AI can be integrated as middleware between existing tools and platforms to ensure compatibility and collaboration between them. It should be emphasized that this makes the overall IT landscape more efficient, flexible, and intelligent (Renner et al., 2025, p. 99). Through integration into the IT landscape, AI can support complex IT projects and, for example, assist employees in customer service (Schneider, 2024, p. 41). In particular, the combination of process mining and AI offers great potential for implementing autonomous and highly automated optimization approaches (Barenkamp & Schnier, 2023, p. 135).

For intelligent RPA solutions, natural language understanding (NLU) can be used to better understand texts and thus improve contact between customers, suppliers, and staff, which leads to a reduction in the workload for employees (Bulander et al., 2022, p. 49). AI agents can also be used. They use large language models (LLMs) to recognize language, but are developing this approach further. They use tools for planning and information processing. Furthermore, they can also perform actual actions (Renner et al., 2025, p. 112).

In summary, the integration of AI into business processes is an evolutionary step for process management. Although the introduction of AI technologies into the service industry is still relatively new, it nevertheless promises to have a significant impact on labor productivity (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1036). Through continuous development and increasing maturity, AI will be able to learn autonomously and optimize itself independently, which includes the adaptation of complex domain knowledge. This results in proactive and predictive capabilities that are necessary for far-reaching optimization and improvement of process execution (Barenkamp & Schnier, 2023, p. 138).

The automation of key areas of work will bring about fundamental economic and social changes (Gentsch, 2018, p. 118). AI can be viewed as a strategic pillar that must be considered across the entire company. It is developing rapidly, and companies must be flexible, adaptable, and constantly keep up with current trends and news (Renner et al., 2025, p. 202). AI-based process optimization

is no longer a vision of the future, but a tangible reality that is significantly changing companies and organizations of all sizes and industries (Renner et al., 2025, p. 71).

2.3 Digital transformation and AI applications in the service industry

Building on the general role of AI in process automation, this chapter focuses on the context of digital transformation in the service industry and its specific characteristics. Digital technologies are no longer just an IT issue, but have become a decisive business factor. The implementation of AI is an important step, particularly in the service sector, as it has characteristics such as a strong customer focus and the need to address individual customer needs (Bruhn & Hadwich, 2023, p. 5). The introduction of GenAI, driven by LLMs, has accelerated this development. It enables new automation possibilities through its interaction using natural language (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 2).

AI is no longer just a topic for companies. It is spreading rapidly and leading to profound changes in the economy and society. Companies are confronted with the question of what impact AI has on the company and how it can be used profitably (Dahm & Schulz, 2024, p. 1). Implementation involves many risks and challenges. Despite these complications, a comprehensive understanding of the implications is essential in order to realize the full potential.

The service sector is experiencing immense pressure to digitize, resulting from the need to ensure long-term competitiveness (Bruhn & Hadwich, 2023, p. 5). The global AI market is projected to reach a volume of USD 405 billion in 2027 (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1036). In addition, approximately 5,154 AI startups have been founded worldwide in the last five years (Bartoletti et al., 2020, p. 3). This illustrates the growth potential and the need for action that goes with it. AI is already shaping various advanced applications, such as self-driving cars, personalized recommendation systems, including medical diagnoses, and voice assistants (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 2).

Key digitalization trends in the German service sector include data-driven approaches and an intense customer focus. AI solutions support decision-making, predict consumer behavior, and identify market trends. The rapid expansion of AI is the result of increasing algorithm complexity, rising data volumes, and improved data collection methods (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1038). It should also be mentioned that AI lags behind in traditional sectors such as construction. This is due to the quantity and quality of data (Blanco et al., 2018, p. 9). In addition to the problems, the service sector also has a major advantage over other sectors, especially in terms of data volume. Nevertheless, there are too few evaluation and process models that help to transform AI technology and methodology into a clear business scenario and added value (Gentsch, 2018, p. 4). There is a shortage of maturity models that can be used for the classification and evaluation of relevant AIs (Gentsch, 2018, p. 16). This paper attempts to close this gap.

AI automation is already being used in the service industry. It ranges from supporting employees in routine administrative tasks to complete automation. In the following, four areas will be examined in more detail, along with their potential for AI implementation.

In marketing, AI solutions such as chatbots, customer identification, and content recommendation fields are used (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1039). This ranges from automated answers to frequently asked questions (FAQs) to proactive problem solving, even before the customer inquiry. The aim is to improve social media engagement, offer personalized online customer experiences, and increase the conversion rate of product suggestions. Special methods such as text mining and machine learning algorithms can be used to identify profitable customer segments (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1039). Potential customers can be analyzed in more detail, and personalized customer contact and individual product offers turn potential customers into loyal customers (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 23). Another important aspect of marketing is market research. There are extensive tools available, such as focus groups, customer surveys, panels, etc., but they involve a great deal of effort. With the help of a bot, thousands of reviews on different platforms can now be analyzed to generate customer statements (Gentsch, 2018, p. 45).

In Finance and Accounting, AI enables the complete automation of time-consuming processes. This includes the valuation of financial transactions and the gathering of evidence for internal audits (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1039). AI is used to detect fraud and make predictions (Fraud Detection) (Gentsch, 2018, p. 45). In accounting, tools such as Accern and Candis are deployed for the analysis of unstructured data in tax calculation (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1042). Banks, in turn, utilize chatbots like Eva and Erica. They reduce labor and transaction costs and increase customer satisfaction and processing efficiency (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1039). Furthermore, AI is also used for the detection and automated trading of stocks. This task was frequently performed by humans, and AI often leads to improvements in efficiency and accuracy (Bartoletti et al., 2020, p. 3).

In Human Resources (HR), AI tools find applications in talent acquisition, turnover analysis, training, and performance analysis. This is achieved by processing employee data and eliminating all subjectivity from the analysis (Anica-Popa et al., 2023, p. 1039). In talent management, AI helps ensure that the highest-quality employees fill key positions. Additionally, patterns necessary for retaining employees longer can be identified. Furthermore, AI can provide training recommendations based on the objective analysis of individual employees (Altenfelder et al., 2025, pp. 29–30). In recruiting, AI can automate the evaluation of applications and the scheduling of interviews for selected candidates (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 29).

In the Consulting Sector, AI applications are also utilized. They take over tasks related to data collection (60 %) and data analysis (70 %), enabling consultants to work more efficiently and making the process more cost-effective (Dahm & Schulz, 2024, p. 20). Especially within internal knowledge systems, a generative application can provide knowledge in a target-group-oriented manner (Dahm & Schulz, 2024, p. 22). Furthermore, AI applications can create small to medium-sized applications, optimize software code, and streamline processes. The advantage here is that the consultant can perform these tasks in the presence of the client and thus better address the client's needs (Dahm & Schulz, 2024, pp. 22–23).

In light of the complex challenges and profound changes associated with the implementation of AI in the German service sector, the necessity of a specific maturity model for this area is underscored. For successful AI scaling, a precise vision, a robust technical architecture, an agile operating model, and a strong focus on human factors are indispensable (Wüst, 2025, p. 4). Companies demonstrating a higher level of digital maturity not only possess a competitive advantage but also achieve higher profits (Westerman et al., 2014, p. 18). This illustrates that this transformation must occur not ad-hoc, but in structured phases, for which specific models can be helpful.

The implementation of AI is faced with organizational, technological, cultural, and legal hurdles. These hurdles can only be overcome through a structured approach. There is currently a lack of practice-oriented literature that supports companies in managing this complexity (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 7). Particularly here, a maturity model can help by creating a roadmap for critical capabilities in the areas of personnel, processes, and tools (Blanco et al., 2018, p. 9). Such a model could evaluate the maturity level of digital transformation and provide recommendations for action for progression to increase the maturity stage. This could advance the implementation of AI in German service sectors, ensuring a coordinated rollout and continuous improvement (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 7).

3 Challenges and success factors of AI implementation for process automation

3.1 Organisationale Dimension

The implementation of AI goes beyond the purely technological level and requires profound organizational adjustments. Many companies lack an adequate understanding of how AI can create business value. As a result, they cannot fully exploit its potential (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 1709). This disruptive potential of AI can provoke anxieties among employees, contributing to the failure of AI implementation. Positive effects during implementation can only be achieved through employee acceptance (Fronczek et al., 2024, pp. 212–213). Consequently, implementation is not merely a technical process, but also requires addressing management-related challenges, such as a lack of expertise or insufficient funding (Tsaih et al., 2023, p. 69).

A clear, comprehensive AI strategy, linked to existing corporate objectives, is essential for realization in order to exploit all the advantages of AI. The strategy will significantly change the collaboration between departments and data management (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 1719). The involvement of executives is essential and should not be left exclusively to technology experts (ibid.). A shared vision is crucial for creating a positive future in which AI facilitates work (Fronczek et al., 2024, p. 217).

The introduction of AI fundamentally changes the working world, as it can be used in almost all areas. The reduction of routine tasks creates freedom for employees, allowing them to concentrate on creative activities (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 1). This transition requires a change from siloed teams to interdisciplinary teams that collaborate across various departments (Fontaine et al., 2021, p. 12).

Additionally, a "new human-centric change management" is required to introduce employees to the topic and alleviate their fears (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 151).

Establishing a robust governance structure is essential for ethical and compliant use (Barenkamp, 2025, p. 4). Additionally, this structure helps legal and corporate functions to minimize data protection and cybersecurity risks (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020, p. 67).

For successful AI implementation, significant investments must be made in technology, data, and human capital. Budgets are needed for implementation. Large, fixed budgets are recommended so that employees have an easier start when developing the AI solution (Enholm et al., 2022, p. 1718). Studies show that successful companies spend more than half of their budget not on the technology itself, but on adoption opportunities (Fountain et al., 2021, p. 14). This underscores that investments in employee and organizational development are just as important as investments in technology (Sarstedt & Wecke, 2022, p. 23).

The greatest risk, however, is not investing in AI, as companies quickly become irrelevant (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 36). It must be considered that AI-based operating models require a longer "cold start" to generate economic value (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020, p. 64). Once this step has been completed, companies can benefit from increased efficiency, for example through a chatbot in customer service (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 58).

In summary, a strategic orientation with a clear vision is important for implementation. Employees must be convinced, and a robust governance structure must be established. Furthermore, targeted investments must be made in technology, but also in the training and further education of personnel.

3.2 Technological dimension

Building on the organizational dimension in Chapter 3.1, this chapter focuses on the technological dimension and its prerequisites for the implementation of AI. The technology offers particular advantages, but also presents some challenges. One study showed that 96%

of executives worldwide discuss the use of AI, but only a single-digit percentage actually implement it (Schneider, 2024, p. 38). In Germany, the problem is that half of the companies that use AI do not use it strategically (Heinrichs, 2024, p. 34). If new software, in this case AI, is not compatible with existing systems, implementation can fail. This is also demonstrated by a case study from the financial sector (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 12). For large companies, the technological barrier is the greatest (45%). Medium-sized companies struggle with a lack of know-how (56%), and for small companies, integration into existing systems (34%) is a major challenge (Heinrichs, 2024, p. 34). In general, various technical hurdles exist, such as the complexity of integrating AI into existing processes, outdated IT infrastructure, inadequate data quantity and quality, increasing security problems, and inefficient data preparation (Thomas, 2024, p. 6).

The performance of AI suffers when data is unstructured, inconsistent, and inaccurate (Tsaih et al., 2023, p. 72). For this reason, there is a need for structured, clean, and accessible data. Another study showed that 52% consider "low-quality and poorly curated datasets" to be a major problem (Thomas, 2024, p. 6). The reason for this is the provision of consistent, processed data. However, this also includes integration from sources such as ERP systems or Data Lakes, which occurs via APIs or RAG systems (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 6). This demonstrates how important data centralization on a unified platform is to make automation truly efficient (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 13).

Connecting new AI systems to the IT infrastructure and legacy systems is a significant challenge. Legacy systems are based on a stable but inflexible architecture, in contrast to modern systems. This results in a discrepancy (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 6). The use of AI as a Service (AlaaS) facilitates access to AI, but challenges also exist here, such as interoperability between different providers, vendor lock-in, and proprietary concerns. Bundling various AlaaS offerings restricts functionalities and complicates the selection of suitable AI components (Tsaih et al., 2023, p. 70). An AI tech-stack model can help improve interoperability between providers and minimize dependency on a single vendor (Tsaih et al., 2023, p. 73).

The implementation of AI pilot projects in the company can be complex, as continuous maintenance and constant adaptation of the systems must be guaranteed. At this point, companies must decide between "build-or-buy". Company-specific solutions are tailored to operations and offer a more valuable development of the core business, whereas an external solution is implemented faster (Raiser do Ó, 2024, p. 16). A proven strategy for gaining valuable insights and realizing modifications is to gradually test a pilot AI project in selected areas (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 7).

Another essential aspect is how to handle cybersecurity (data leaks, attacks on algorithms) and how these must be proactively managed. Concerns regarding data protection and security have increased. In 2023, 34% of companies had concerns, and in 2024, this figure rose to 41% (Thomas, 2024, p. 6). This increase could be related to the introduction of the EU AI Act. Clear guidelines must be formulated by companies that govern the use of corporate data with AI tools in order to guarantee data security (Schneider, 2024, p. 40). An example of this is the financial sector, which is highly regulated and places strict demands on IT. These include data localization, end-to-end encryption, and regular security audits to protect against the misuse of sensitive data (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 6).

In summary, it can be stated that a robust data infrastructure and seamless system integration are major technical challenges in the integration of AI solutions and require careful planning. A sound technical basis is essential for implementing AI into intelligent process automation.

3.3 Cultural dimension and employee acceptance

This chapter addresses the human factors that are often neglected in the implementation of AI with regard to process automation. Despite the promising potential of AI, many organizations cannot meet these expectations because technology is not the biggest challenge, but culture (Fontaine et al.,

2021, p. 10). This is also reflected in the slow implementation of AI and the necessity to restructure the organization, as cultural and structural barriers significantly alter the AI initiative (Fountain et al., 2021, p. 12). Employees develop concerns and anxieties regarding profound change. This ambivalence shows that human factors, in particular, are an underestimated dimension in the implementation of AI (Bruhn & Hadwich, 2023, p. V).

Employees' greatest fear is linked to job loss, as new skills will be required because the technology will take over certain tasks previously performed by human workers (Bruhn & Hadwich, 2023, p. 38). This fear is particularly pronounced in the low-wage sector and for jobs with low qualification requirements (Bruhn & Hadwich, 2023, p. 31). In addition to job loss, the fear of losing control is a key concern. The lack of transparency and the complexity of AI decisions can lead employees to feel they are losing control over the process and do not understand the logic behind the AI's decisions (Hüsch et al., 2023, p. 21). This phenomenon, known as the "black box phenomenon," was already discussed in Chapter 2.1.

For successful AI implementation, all employees and executives must acquire new skills and "AI literacy." Employees must learn how to achieve good collaboration with AI while simultaneously making the best possible use of their human strengths such as empathy, creativity, and strategic thinking (Altenfelder et al., 2025, p. 1). To promote AI literacy, companies should offer further education or training. Internal academies can be utilized for this purpose, from top executives down to end-users. These options offer various learning formats, such as classroom instruction, workshops, and on-the-job training (Fountain et al., 2021, p. 17).

To manage the organizational change during AI introduction and to involve the workforce, proactive change management and transparent communication are necessary. The development of clear guidelines and standards for implementation is essential (Hüsch et al., 2023, p. 15). A proven strategy is to involve employees as early as possible so that they feel more motivated, informed, and included (Heinrichs, 2024, p. 33). Transparent communication must show the benefits, but also the challenges, in order to reduce fears and create understanding and acceptance (Hüsch et al., 2023, p. 19). Leaders, in particular, must convey a vision to employees in which AI enhances their role rather than eliminating it (Fountain et al., 2021, p. 13).

Creating a culture that tolerates mistakes and promotes continuous learning is necessary for the long-term success of AI implementation. Companies must discard the mindset that they have to completely plan a project before implementing it. A "test-and-learn" mentality must be established, which views errors as a source of discovery and reduces the fear of failure (Fountain et al., 2021, p. 12). The task of management is to create an environment that encourages innovation and expertise (Hüsch et al., 2023, p. 18). This is achieved with pilot projects. They give employees insight into the technologies and spark enthusiasm by allowing them to experience the practical implementation within the company (Bruhn & Hadwich, 2023, p. 38).

In summary, it can be stated in this section that creating a positive corporate culture, promoting AI skills, and implementing proactive change management are necessary to guarantee employee acceptance. The collaboration between humans and AI should be designed to support and complement humans rather than replacing them (Hüscher et al., 2023, p. 29).

3.4 Legal and ethical aspects

This chapter addresses the relevant importance of legal and ethical frameworks that are necessary for the use of AI, particularly in the service sector, which mostly operates with sensitive data. This sensitive data, such as financial data, is subject to strict regulatory requirements, which poses a major challenge with regard to data protection and data security (Hüscher et al., 2023, p. 2). If AI is implemented carelessly or maliciously, it can lead to harm, such as discrimination, or the AI may reinforce a bias (see Chapter 2.1) (Veale & Binns, 2017, p. 1). The increasing skepticism of customers regarding the handling of sensitive data and the urgency of protecting data correctly contributes to the necessity for companies to engage intensively with the legal and ethical frameworks.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a central regulatory framework that governs the processing and storage of personal data. It has been mandatory in all EU countries since 2018 (Hüscher et al., 2023, p. 130). The purpose of data protection is to protect personal data from misuse and to guarantee the right to informational self-determination (ibid.). The GDPR has several core principles. The principle of purpose limitation (Art. 5 para. 1 in the GDPR) demonstrates that data may only be collected for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes, and that processing exclusively serves this purpose (Bartoletti et al., 2020, p. 211).

Another important approach is the data minimization principle. It stipulates that personal data must be adequate, relevant, and limited to the minimum necessary. A significant hurdle in this regard is that it contradicts the principles required for a well-trained AI (Bartoletti et al., 2020, p. 212). Companies are obligated to obtain consent from the data subjects for the processing and storage of their data (Hüscher et al., 2023, p. 130). If a data processing operation poses a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) must be carried out (Hüscher et al., 2023, p. 132).

Central importance in the use of AI systems is placed on transparency, fairness, accountability, and the avoidance of discrimination. AI can make unfair decisions by adopting biases from historical data (Veale & Binns, 2017, p. 1). This bias can arise from various reasons, including data, algorithms, or user interactions (Hüscher et al., 2023, p. 24). A defining example of this is the COMPAS tool, which in the US falsely categorized Black defendants as twice as likely to commit violent offenses as white defendants (Shum, 2023, p. 217).

The use of algorithmic systems can lead to risks, such as a pseudoscientific legitimization for decisions that would be vulnerable to challenge if made by a human (Veale & Binns, 2017, p. 1). Ethical aspects

include the conflict between the goals of efficiency and transparency (explainability) of AI systems. Both intended and unintended consequences must be understood (Bartoletti et al., 2020, p. 171).

To ensure a responsible and legally compliant use of AI in companies, ethical guidelines and robust governance mechanisms are crucial. A strategic challenge for companies is defining the responsibilities and tasks for the implementation, operation, and management of AI (Breiter et al., 2025, p. 5). Five ethical principles are particularly important: transparency, justice and fairness, non-maleficence, accountability, and privacy (Vayena et al., 2019, p. 1). The EU Commission's draft legislation (AI Act) aims to provide safeguards by defining AI systems in a technology-independent manner and establishing rules based on four risk assessments:

- Unacceptable risk: These are prohibited because they violate EU values.
- High risk: Mandatory requirements apply in critical areas, such as surgery.
- Limited risk: There is a limited number of obligations, such as transparency requirements.
- Low risk: All other AI systems whose development and use comply with existing EU legislation (Shum, 2023, p. 227).

In summary, robust governance is essential, which not only protects the company from complaints but also from legal consequences. The GDPR and the AI Act are laws that every company in the EU must comply with. Furthermore, companies should develop standards for the implementation and processing of AI that ideally go beyond legal requirements.

3.5 Practical perspectives on implementation barriers: findings from exploratory interviews

This chapter presents the central findings from the empirical data collection, obtained through expert interviews with three representatives from the respective different areas of the German service sector (Insurance Industry E1, IT Consulting E2, and Banking E3). The interviews primarily serve to validate and concretize the dimensions theoretically derived in Chapters 3.1 to 3.4. All experts agree that neglecting a complete dimension "inevitably leads to the failure" of the AI initiative (Expert E1). The subsequent structure assigns the empirical findings to the four theoretical dimensions and provides crucial input for the development of the maturity model in Chapter 4.

Table 1: List of experts (own representation)

EXPERTE (ANONYMOUS)	INDUSTRY(FICTITIOUS, BUT REPRESENTATIVE)	ROLE/FOCUS
EXPERTE 1 (E1)	Financial services/insurance	Head of Data & AI
EXPERTE 2 (E2)	IT-Consulting & Retail	Specialist in end-to-end automation
EXPERTE 3 (E3)	Banking industry	Transformation Manager

Organizational Challenges

The biggest organizational hurdle in AI implementation lies not in the initial feasibility study (Proof-of-Concept), but in the broad, company-wide scaling after the completion of pilot projects (Expert E1). A prerequisite is that AI is integrated into the company's objectives. Targeted prioritization of projects based on their expected business value is essential in this regard (Expert E1, Expert E3).

Establishing a central Center of Excellence (CoE) is essential to enable controlled scaling. This functions as a knowledge and control center that sets standards (Expert E2, Expert E3). To support scalability, the implementation of a "Hub-and-Spoke" model is necessary to distribute strategic responsibility from the headquarters to the business units (Expert E1). When starting, simple use cases should be sought that enable quick success and testing (Expert E2). An indicator of high maturity is the ability not only to automate existing processes but also to proactively redesign end-to-end processes (Re-Engineering) (Expert E2). Before a process is automated, it should first be optimized. A bad process remains bad even when automated (Expert E1).

Technological challenges

Good data quality and data availability are in every respect the minimum (must-have) for every AI application (Expert E1, Expert E2, Expert E3). The technological challenges primarily lie in the fragmentation of data stored in various data silos. This requires accessing data in a legacy system, which experts consider a time-consuming component of projects (Expert E3).

The lack of standardized tool platforms slows down scaling in earlier project phases (Expert E2). Therefore, initial exploration should take place in a technically secure environment (Expert E1). This can ensure the stability and scalability of the IT infrastructure for subsequent transformations (Expert E3). Another important point that emerged from the interview is that companies that are cloud-savvy have an easier entry point into the introduction of AI (Expert E1, Expert E3).

At a higher level of maturity, decisions must be consistently made. At this point, it is advisable to make data-driven decisions (Expert E3). Cybersecurity and IT risk management were not a new topic for any expert due to AI. Rather, they were already established in the corporate identity. Expert 1 explained that every integrated component of AI projects undergoes a risk impact assessment.

Cultural challenges

In theory, the shift towards AI automation is influenced by significant cultural factors. Employee anxieties or loss of control, in particular, are repeatedly emphasized. However, in all the interviews that were conducted, very few complaints or fears were expressed. Expert E2 stated regarding the topic of job loss that middle management at their clients' companies had the greatest concerns about loss of control. Another cultural hurdle is the belief that AI automation can be beneficial and the need to

obtain the associated approval from upper management (Expert E3). After approval, however, unrealistic expectation management can arise. People believe that AI is "magic" that solves problems they themselves cannot describe (Expert E1). There is a lack not only of AI specialists but also of a basic understanding of AI (Expert E1, Expert E2, Expert E3). Employee trust must be gained. This can be achieved by offering company-wide training and providing easy access to general-purpose AI so that employees can experience the opportunities firsthand (Expert E1).

Legal and ethical challenges

Since the German service sector is one of the most heavily regulated markets, compliance and security are fundamental requirements that must be ensured from the very beginning of the exploration phase (Expert E1, Expert E2). The current regulatory uncertainty surrounding the EU AI Act is causing some of Expert E2's clients to pause or delay their high-risk AI projects.

There is a growing need for Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) for decisions of great importance (Expert E2). Legal and ethical aspects must be integrated into a basic governance framework early on (Expert E2). Expert E1 spoke about the "Human in the Loop" (HITL) principle. In the case of an automated decision by the AI, a human control instance checks whether the decision is correct. The legal frameworks are thus not subsequent points, but significantly determine the technical feasibility of AI systems.

4 Development of a maturity model for AI implementation for process automation in the German service industry

4.1 Theoretical foundations of maturity models and methodological approach to model development

The challenges of AI implementation for process automation in the German service sector require a structured, methodical approach. The hurdles and potentials identified in Chapters 2 and 3 show that companies need a holistic instrument. It should support them in analyzing their situation using evaluation criteria and, based on this, creating systematic recommendations for action. The development of a maturity model is suitable for this purpose.

4.1.1 Definition, purpose, and structure of maturity models

A maturity model evaluates the maturity of a unit in several stages, which can be processes or organizations, for example (Mangiapane & Büchler, 2024, p. 13). This is a system that can be used by organizations or individuals to set continuous benchmarks for process improvement (Shang & Lin, 2009, p. 510). In this context, the term maturity describes a gradual improvement of capabilities or goals, starting from an initial phase up to a final phase (Limat, 2022, p. 62).

The current status in a specific area is thus evaluated, and based on this assessment, improvements are ultimately made (Hochkamp et al., 2025, p. 2). This evaluation is based on a target state for

organizations or processes (ibid.). A current state (Is-Zustand) is analyzed, and recommendations for action are derived to close the gap to the target state (Soll-Zustand) (Mangiapane & Büchler, 2024, p. 14). This is particularly important because the discrepancy between the actual and target states must be resolved (Mangiapane & Büchler, 2024, p. 23). Due to this division into phases and the continuous prospect of improvement, the maturity model is excellently suited as a decision-making instrument for the implementation of AI in companies.

The structure of such models can vary greatly. This may be because different companies have different goals, but most models are based on certain core principles. Essential features include design levels, dimensions, objects, and maturity levels. Additionally, the model can also be based on a TOE framework (Technology, Organization, Environment) (Limat, 2022, p. 62). Another model categorizes the influencing factors into the groups "Technical requirements", "Expert knowledge" and "Administration" (Hochkamp et al., 2025, p. 16). Thus, it can be recognized that there are different models for different goals. However, what connects all models is that each maturity level has specific goals and methods for improvement (Shang & Lin, 2009, p. 510).

The stages of the maturity model sequence a development path, whereby no stage can be skipped. The capabilities from a lower stage serve as the foundation for reaching the next higher stage (Shang & Lin, 2009, p. 510). A maturity model can, for example, have 6 stages, from Level 0 to Level 5. The assessment is typically carried out using questionnaires (Mangiapane & Büchler, 2024, p. 13). A maturity model creates a holistic and multifaceted picture of the current state (Mangiapane & Büchler, 2024, p. 79). This approach helps to manage complexity and control the strategic implementation of AI within the company (Ramdhani & Surendro, 2022, p. 145).

4.1.2 Analysis of existing maturity models in digitalization and AI implementation (with a focus on identified gaps)

The present work aims to develop a maturity model for the strategic implementation of AI for process automation in the German service sector. To demonstrate the necessity of this model, a systematic analysis and critical evaluation of existing models is essential. This chapter will introduce various models from the literature and illuminate their strengths and weaknesses with regard to the research question, thereby identifying a clear research gap that my model aims to close.

The analysis focused on the following models, which represent different approaches:

Thordsen and Bick (2023): A comprehensive literature review that provides a critical overview of the field of research on digital maturity models and already points to fundamental gaps in theory and practice.

Noymanee et al. (2022): A model that explicitly addresses AI maturity, but with a specific industry focus on the public sector.

Omol et al. (2025): A model developed for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that takes a holistic view of digitalization but does not include specific AI or ethical dimensions.

Gökalp and Martinez (2022): A methodologically sound model for digital transformation that covers many of our dimensions, but does not explicitly consider legal and ethical aspects and is primarily focused on the manufacturing industry.

Through the critical examination of these models, it is demonstrated that a holistic solution that focuses on AI-supported process automation in the German service sector is missing in current research. The results from the analysis serve as a further theoretical basis for my maturity model.

1. Modell: "A decade of digital maturity models: much ado about nothing?" by Thordsen and Bick (2023)

This is not an independent maturity model, but rather a systematic literature review on the current state of Digital Maturity Models (DMMs). The aim is to present a central discussion in the research field that questions the practical and theoretical value of DMMs and to capture a research agenda for the future (Thordsen & Bick, 2023, pp. 947–949). The authors analyzed 64 publications to comprehensively present the topic (Thordsen & Bick, 2023, p. 954).

The most common dimensions used in DMMs for evaluating digital maturity are: Technology, Digital Culture, Operational Processes, Digital Strategy, and Management (Leadership and Performance) (Thordsen & Bick, 2023, p. 950). This confirms the relevance of the dimensions, as some of them also serve as a basis for my model. Furthermore, Thordsen and Bick mentioned that DMMs must be applied specifically to use cases, as generic models do not provide added value (ibid.).

Trotz der großen Relevanz dieses Modells existieren ein paar Lücken, die weitere Forschung erforderlich machen. Die Besonderheit des Dienstleistungssektors wird nicht erwähnt. Die meisten domänenspezifischen Ansätze fokussieren sich auf das Gewerbe oder den allgemeinen Geschäftskontext (Thordsen & Bick, 2023, S. 950) Zudem fehlt eine eigenständige Dimension für rechtliche und ethische Aspekte. Hinzu kommt, dass KI in dem Modell nicht als eigenständiges Thema behandelt wird.

Despite the great relevance of this model, a few gaps exist that necessitate further research. The specific characteristics of the service sector are not mentioned. Most domain-specific approaches focus on trade or the general business context (Thordsen & Bick, 2023, p. 950). Furthermore, a separate dimension for legal and ethical aspects is lacking. Additionally, AI is not treated as a distinct topic within the model.

2. Model: Analysis of the AI maturity model by Noymanee et al. (2022)

Another relevant model that directly addresses AI maturity is the "Artificial Intelligence Maturity Model for Government Administration and Service" by Noymanee et al. (2022). The model deals with AI

implementation in the public sector and supports organizations in evaluating their AI capability (Noymanee et al., 2022, p. 66).

The model possesses a clear structure and is closely aligned with the dimensions I defined. It evaluates AI maturity based on four main areas: the "Strategic aspects," the "Organizational aspects," "Information," and "Technology" (Noymanee et al., 2022, p. 69). Within the strategic aspects, ethical considerations are specifically included as evaluation criteria, which distinguishes it from many other models (ibid.). This concept represents a valuable template for my maturity model because it integrates all relevant dimensions into a coherent framework.

Despite the strengths of the model, specific gaps can be found through my research question. The biggest limitation of this model is its industry focus. The model is designed for the public sector and therefore cannot be readily applied to the private service sector (Noymanee et al., 2022, p. 69). The objectives of public authorities and private companies differ significantly. Furthermore, references to Germany and Europe are missing, where different regulations apply, such as the GDPR or the EU AI Act, which are of central importance to my work. The model also treats process automation more as a broad application of AI and not as a detailed, measurable core area.

The model by Noymanee et al. (2022) is an excellent reference to demonstrate how AI-focused maturity models are structured. At the same time, it offers a clear demarcation by showing that such a model is not yet tailored for the German private sector.

3. Modell: Analyse des Digital Maturity Assessment Model (DMAM) von Omol et al. (2025)

The model by Omol et al. (2025) refers to the assessment of the digital maturity of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Omol et al., 2025, p. 128). The model was developed to fill the gap of missing tailored models for resource-independent SMEs and to provide them with a practical guide for their digitalization (ibid.). Methodologically, the DMAM is based on Design Science Research (DSR) and the Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI), which demonstrates its scientific and structural strength (ibid.).

The DMAM covers important dimensions of digitalization, including Technology, People, Organization, Strategy, and Operations (Omol et al., 2025, p. 130). The authors decided that these dimensions are the most important for SMEs. What is special about this model compared to the previous models is that the "People" dimension is highlighted (Omol et al., 2025, p. 137). It is emphasized how crucial employee acceptance and change management are. Therefore, the model is a valuable reference for the conception of my model (ibid.).

Despite its methodological strength and relevance for SMEs, the DMAM exhibits specific research gaps. The model focuses on general digitalization and does not specifically focus on AI. The application of AI is not a separate or measurable dimension, which proves a clear research gap.

Furthermore, the model neglects legal and ethical aspects, as the authors did not consider these relevant enough. This results in the problem that it therefore does not include the GDPR and the EU AI Act.

The DMAM is an excellent reference that demonstrates how maturity models are methodologically sound and empirically validated. At the same time, it serves as a gap for my model by focusing on AI automation, ethical aspects, and the German service sector.

4. Model: Analysis of the Digital Transformation Capability Maturity Model (DX-CMM) by Gökalp and Martinez (2022)

The model was developed to address the lack of methodological foundation in many existing maturity models. It uses the established standard SPICE as a basis and provides organizations with a structured way to assess their digital maturity (Gökalp & Martinez, 2022, p. 6283). The model is divided into two dimensions: a process dimension and a capability dimension. The process dimension comprises four groups (Gökalp & Martinez, 2022, p. 6282): Strategic Governance, Information and Technology, Digital Process Transformation, and Workforce Management. The structure is extremely relevant as it offers a holistic overview for various digital fields of action (Gökalp & Martinez, 2022, p. 6288).

Nevertheless, the model also has weaknesses. It is a generic model that is not specific enough. Furthermore, AI is only discussed as one of many ideas (Gökalp & Martinez, 2022, p. 6285). This clearly demonstrates a thematic gap with regard to AI process automation. Additionally, legal and ethical aspects are not considered. The authors themselves admit that there is a gap that is not included in any of the 18 models they examined. Due to the GDPR and the EU AI Act, a gap exists here that my model attempts to close. Moreover, the model is primarily intended for the manufacturing industry, even though the authors emphasize that the model is applicable across all sectors.

The DX-CMM by Gökalp and Martinez (2022) is scientifically sound and provides a good basis for the conception of a maturity model. However, the gap of the missing ethical and legal focus, as well as the focus on the manufacturing industry, justifies why a new, tailored model needs to be developed.

4.1.3 Design science research as a research approach and model development process (including the role of interviews as input for the dimensions)

For the development of a practice-oriented maturity model, a methodological foundation is used. The chosen approach for this is Design Science Research (DSR). DSR can be used for both small-scale university studies and for extensive applications. The central idea is the development of innovative artifacts to solve real-world problems (Humble & Mozelius, 2023, p. 87). The problem paradigm aims to establish innovations in the analysis, design, implementation, management, and use of information systems in order to structure them more effectively and efficiently (Hevner et al., 2004, p. 76).

DSR is a creative approach in which human and organizational capabilities are enhanced through innovative methods, models, or systems (Chatterjee et al., 2023, p. 803). This approach not only solves problems but also generates new knowledge. The application area of DSR has an engineering and management-oriented focus, ranging from system development to the management of innovative resources (ibid.).

The research process for developing a maturity model is iterative and follows the principles of DSR. The process is usually divided into different phases such as problem identification, artifact development, evaluation, and communication (Chatterjee et al., 2023, p. 803).

The scientific process can be divided into different cycles: a Relevance Cycle, a Design Cycle, and a Rigor Cycle. The cycles influence each other and are traversed in different phases of the research work (Alex & Robra-Bissantz, 2024, p. 804). The central element of DSR is the "building and evaluating" of artifacts (Weigand & Johannesson, 2023, p. 1). The development process is thus an iterative process consisting of the two main activities (Hevner et al., 2004, p. 78).

The model development process in this work can be divided into five phases, based on Johannesson and Perjons (Humble & Mozelius, 2023, p. 87).

1. Problem Identification and Motivation: At the beginning of the research, a practical problem requiring action must be identified. The necessity of a systematic approach to AI implementation can be defined as this problem.
2. Objective of the Artifact: After identifying a problem, a goal is derived for the model, which should represent a solution.
3. Design and Development of the Artifact: In this phase, the maturity model is conceived. Models assume the role of "design objects" (Weigand & Johannesson, 2023, p. 4). The literature analysis (Rigor Cycle) and the insights gained from the interviews (Relevance Cycle) form the basis for designing the dimensions, maturity levels, and indicators.
4. Demonstration and Evaluation: The functionality of the model is demonstrated through an example, and its usefulness, quality, and effectiveness are assessed (Hevner et al., 2004, p. 85).
5. The results of the research project are made available in this work to the academic community as well as for practical application.

The expert interviews are of great importance in the development of the maturity model. They serve as qualitative sources and are intended to help uncover the problem and solution space during the course of the project. The practical insights gained from the interviews complement the theoretically derived dimensions and ensure that the model has high practical relevance.

4.2 Presentation of the maturity model

This chapter is dedicated to the central part of the thesis. Building on the theoretical foundations and the methodological approach, the chapter begins with a defining vision and objective. This is followed by the detailed description of the vision. Next is the definition of the maturity levels per dimension. Finally, indicators and assessment criteria for each maturity level and dimension are defined.

4.2.1 Vision and objectives of the model

The challenge of AI in process automation is a holistic process and requires a structured approach. Building on the previous chapters, theoretical and practical hurdles are identified. This chapter is dedicated to presenting the maturity model as a central artifact. It closes the research gap of a lack of industry- and application-specific focus. The vision and objectives are a very important aspect of a maturity model and should answer the questions: Why does this model exist? What functions does it have? And who is it intended for?

The vision for this model is to support the German service sector in the strategic implementation of AI in process automation. It is intended to serve as a systematic guide for companies, leading them toward an integrated, data-driven, and strategically aligned "algorithmic enterprise." Implementation is not conceived as a one-time project, but as a continuous transformation process that encompasses all relevant dimensions of the company.

The objectives for the model can be divided into three core areas:

Positioning and gap analysis: The model enables managers and process owners to objectively assess the current maturity level of the company in five defined dimensions (strategy & governance, data & technology, processes & automation, culture & competence, law & ethics). Such a systematic evaluation highlights the key deficits and the greatest potential for development. This is of central importance, as an analysis of the current situation is a fundamental prerequisite for goal-oriented planning.

Provision of a clear roadmap: The maturity model serves as a pragmatic guide for gradual progression from a lower to a higher level of maturity. It offers companies more than just an analysis; it also derives recommendations for action to close the identified gaps. This enables the development from experimental to controlled and ultimately successful use of AI.

Support for strategic planning: The model is not only used for actual analysis, but is also intended to be used as a tool for strategic planning. It helps companies set priorities and make the right investments. It also creates a common basis for communication for all stakeholders involved in the AI transformation. This is a crucial factor in reducing complexity and ensuring a structured introduction.

The concept therefore relates directly to the German service industry, which is characterized by a high degree of complexity and has a specific need for a holistic solution approach. It helps companies

move away from purely technical implementation and incorporate all relevant success factors to ensure a clear and logical approach to increasing their AI maturity level.

4.2.2 Detailed description of the dimensions

The identified challenges and success factors form the conceptual foundation for the maturity model that has been developed. AI implementation for process automation goes beyond the purely technological level. It is an integral transformation process that involves all areas of a company. Based on theoretical findings from the literature and practical findings from expert interviews, the maturity model is divided into five dimensions. These dimensions represent critical areas of action that companies must systematically address in order to increase AI maturity. To ensure intuitive and quick positioning, the dimensions and the associated maturity are visualized in a spider web diagram.

Strategy & Governance

This dimension is dedicated to the strategic integration of AI automation and the establishment of clear control mechanisms. It ensures that the AI initiative is not implemented in isolation, but in a targeted manner and in line with business objectives. A high level of maturity in this dimension implies that implementation is no longer a purely ad hoc experiment. Rather, it is based on a clear, targeted strategy supported by the use of dedicated resources, the definition of responsibilities, and an effective governance structure.

Practical experience shows that the critical hurdles for organizations are not proof-of-concept testing, but rather scaling pilot projects to the enterprise level. The introduction of central control bodies such as centers of excellence (CoE) or the implementation of a hub-and-spoke model can help with coordination in order to achieve greater maturity. Projects should be prioritized according to their expected business value in order to make optimal use of limited resources. A lack of strategic alignment is, as in the literature and in practice, a major cause of AI project failure.

Data & Technology

This dimension deals with data and technology, as these form the fundamental basis of AI. AI systems are data-driven, and their performance depends directly on the quality, quantity, and accessibility of the data. For this reason, this dimension addresses the entire infrastructure: from data collection, data management, and data quality to system integration and scalability of AI solutions. A high level of maturity in this dimension is characterized by a stable and scalable data infrastructure, smooth system integration, and effective data quality management.

In practice, data quality and data availability are also a must-have. The interviews revealed that there is a problem with the integration of legacy systems and the associated fragmentation in data silos. Companies that are cloud-savvy find it easier to get started with AI implementation in this dimension. In addition, initial explorations should be carried out in a technically secure environment to ensure

that the IT infrastructure is secure for subsequent transformations. A risk impact assessment for AI projects should be prepared for each integrated component.

Processes & Automation

This dimension focuses on the integration of AI into operational business processes. It evaluates whether AI technology goes beyond traditional, rule-based automation (RPA) to handle complex tasks. Greater maturity in this dimension implies that AI systems not only handle individual tasks, but also transform entire end-to-end processes. The highest level of maturity is achieved when companies are able to continuously improve their processes through AI-supported analysis and hyperautomation. This not only increases efficiency gains, but also improves the quality of decisions and value creation.

The experts provide essential methods for process automation. The process must first be optimized before it can be automated. This critical preliminary analysis is necessary because "a bad process remains bad even when automated." Theory and experts agree that a high level of maturity is characterized by the ability to proactively redesign end-to-end processes (reengineering).

Culture & Skills

In many cases, the culture and skills of employees are not taken into account. However, it has been shown that the human factor is closely linked to the success of an AI transformation. This dimension assesses employee acceptance, willingness to change, and the associated skills. A high level of maturity is achieved when the company actively addresses employees' fears about AI. At the same time, targeted change management and training prepare employees for working with intelligent systems.

The insights gained from the interviews shed light on the cultural challenges from a differentiated perspective. There is too little skepticism or fear among employees. Concerns about loss of control are primarily found among middle management. From the experts' point of view, there is a lack of basic understanding of AI, and employees have unrealistic expectations, believing that AI is "magic." Employee confidence is strengthened by easy access and a "test and learn" mentality.

Law & Ethics

Compliance with legal and ethical frameworks is particularly important in the service sector. This dimension assesses measures taken to comply with the GDPR. It is also necessary to ensure that AI operates in a transparent, fair, and responsible manner. A high level of maturity in this dimension implies that the company proactively addresses the guidelines and establishes a strong governance structure to secure the trust of stakeholders. The dimension emphasizes the need for AI to go beyond a purely technical consideration and be understood as a legal and ethical system.

The expert interviews confirm that compliance and security are fundamental requirements from the exploration phase onwards in the highly regulated German service sector. This dimension is hampered by uncertainty among employees: many companies are putting AI projects on hold due to the uncertainty surrounding the EU AI Act. Practice shows that there is a greater need for explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) for decisions of great importance. As a concrete measure to comply with legal standards and control risk, the "human in the loop" (HITL) principle is applied, whereby a human control authority reviews automated decisions.

Figure 1: Spinning diagram of the maturity model (own representation)

4.2.3 Definition of maturity levels

The clear definition of maturity levels is a key element in the development of the maturity model. It represents a progressive development of the previously defined dimensions. Each level, from "Initial" to "Optimized," describes the state of AI implementation for process automation. This scale enables companies to assess their current status and serves as a template for step-by-step improvement. The design of the maturity levels stipulates that fulfillment of the criteria for a lower level is a prerequisite for a higher level.

Level 1: Initial

This is the basic level. The implementation of AI is characterized by an uncontrolled approach. There is no coherent strategy or vision for the use of AI. Projects carried out at this level are mostly individual initiatives and are not linked to business objectives. Data is stored in silos and is unstructured and therefore of poor quality, which makes the use of AI difficult. Technologies are used in isolation and there is no common platform. Processes are carried out manually. Culturally, employees reject AI and the necessary skills are lacking within the company. Legal and ethical frameworks are neither addressed nor are there any clear guidelines.

Stage 2: Fragmented

This stage is characterized by initial attempts to use AI in selected areas. The first pilot projects are launched in departments that are considered "early adopters." However, there is no company-wide AI strategy, and the projects are carried out in isolation. Data and technology are structured and cleaned up in some areas, but there is no central data strategy. Technologies are mostly used in isolated solutions. In terms of processes and automation, AI projects are tested in non-critical areas, such as simple chatbots. Culturally, training courses are offered and the first teams of experts are formed.

Level 3: Established

At this level, AI implementation is approached systematically and in a standardized manner. It is therefore no longer an isolated issue. A formal AI strategy is in place and integrated into the company's objectives. There are designated responsible parties and an initial governance structure. Data and technology are centralized, investments are made in data lakes, and there is a clear standard for data quality management. Processes are increasingly documented and standardized, with AI applications contributing to value creation in core processes. Culturally, change management is more actively pursued, and training and development programs equip employees with the necessary skills. Legal and ethical frameworks are established and proactively taken into account in project planning.

Level 4: Systematic

This level is characterized by data-driven and optimized use of AI. Governance is fully integrated into the corporate culture, and performance is constantly monitored and measured using defined key performance indicators (KPIs). Companies use a robust data infrastructure that enables them to perform advanced analyses. Processes are optimized by AI, and they are able to make forward-looking decisions. The company is able to perform real-time analyses and adjust results based on them. Culturally, there is a strong data-driven mindset. Employees work together intelligently in hybrid teams. Legal and ethical aspects are continuously monitored by automated monitoring systems to ensure security and transparency.

Level 5: Optimized

At the highest level, AI is no longer just a tool, but the heart of innovation and the basis for the business model. Strategy and governance are fully integrated into AI, and technology drives the emergence of new business areas. The data and technology infrastructure is highly developed and enables the use of autonomous AI systems. Processes are not only optimized in real time, but also adapt dynamically. Culturally, employees focus on strategic and creative tasks, while AI takes over routine work. The company is a pioneer and develops further standards for the responsible use of AI and the associated legal and ethical standards.

4.2.4 Indicators and evaluation criteria for each maturity level and dimension

The description of the dimensions and the definition of maturity levels in the previous chapters play a central role in the development of the maturity model. However, in order to use the theoretical concepts in an applicable instrument, indicators and evaluation criteria are needed. These are intended to help companies transfer their current status into the maturity model. The criteria are presented in matrix form. They serve as a practical checklist for evaluation, which is applied in Chapter 5 using examples.

The criteria are selected on the basis of chapters 2 and 3 and the resulting challenges and success factors, as well as the analysis of existing models. It serves to determine the maturity of a company not only qualitatively but also quantitatively. It thus also provides a solid basis for concrete recommendations for action.

Table 2: Indicators Table for assessing maturity (own representation)

Maturity Level	Strategy & Governance	Data & Technology	Processes & Automation	Culture & Competencies	Law & Ethics
Level 1: Initial	No formal AI strategy exists, projects are isolated ad-hoc initiatives.	Data is stored in silos and there is no systematic process for data cleansing or management.	Processes are manual or automated through simple, rule-based scripts.	Employees are skeptical about AI and no training courses are offered.	No guidelines exist for dealing with AI, and legal issues are handled ad-hoc.
Level 2: Fragmented	First AI pilot projects were started in individual departments without an overarching vision.	Data is collected and prepared project-specifically, without a central data strategy.	AI solutions are being tested in non-critical sub-processes (e.g., simple chatbots).	First small expert teams drive the topic forward; informal training takes place.	Awareness of data protection and ethics is growing, but there are no mandatory guidelines.
Level 3: Established	A formal AI strategy is integrated into the corporate goals and clear responsibilities exist (e.g., CoE/Hub-and-Spoke established).	Data from all relevant departments is built up in a central, company-wide platform (Data Lake/Warehouse), and standards for data quality management exist (exploration in a secured environment).	AI applications are integrated into core processes and contribute to value creation (processes were optimized beforehand).	Formal change management accompanies the AI introduction, structured training programs exist (start to address the unrealistic expectation management).	Ethical guidelines and compliance structures are established and are taken into account in project planning.
Level 4: Systematic	The success of AI projects is systematically measured and monitored using KPIs, and regular reviews take place.	The data infrastructure is robust and scalable, and predictive analytics are used for process control (Consistent data-driven decisions).	Processes optimize themselves autonomously through AI analysis, and real-time analyses are possible (Capability for End-to-End Process Re-Engineering).	The "Test-and-Learn" mentality in dealing with new technologies is firmly anchored in the corporate culture (Addressing management fears).	AI systems are regularly checked for algorithmic bias and the "Human in the Loop" (HITL) principle is applied (Increasing need for XAI).
Level 5: Optimized	AI is the core of the business strategy and actively drives business model innovation.	Data is a strategic competitive advantage; sophisticated, autonomous AI systems are utilized.	Hyper-automation is established, and processes adapt dynamically and in real-time.	AI integration is a natural part of the corporate culture; employees focus on strategic tasks.	The company sets standards for the responsible use of AI and acts as a pioneer in the industry.

An operational checklist in the form of a yes/no matrix was developed to carry out the exemplary model evaluation. This checklist represents the final artifact of the design science research approach used in this work and can be found in Appendix (2) for specific application.

4.3 Recommendations for action regarding the transition between maturity levels

The previous chapter precisely defined the dimensions and levels for the maturity model. It is intended to help move from the current actual state to the desired target state. In order to derive practical benefits from the model, it is necessary to develop actionable recommendations based on the assessment. This chapter deals with how German service companies can establish continuous improvement in AI maturity. The aim of the recommendations is to enable companies to recognize the challenges and address them systematically. It should also facilitate a coordinated transition to the next level and serve as a guide for achieving a data-driven and AI-enabled organization.

4.3.1 General recommendations for action for each maturity level

A step-by-step process for increasing AI maturity has different priorities at each stage. The following recommendations for action are designed to help companies move on to the next stage and thus enable continuous improvement.

From maturity level 1 (initial) to 2 (fragmented)

The transition from the first to the second phase requires raising awareness and identifying potential. The key recommendation is to start with small pilot projects (e.g., customer service chatbot, simple document analysis) in order to quickly demonstrate their added value. The focus is on so-called quick wins to increase employee acceptance. The feasibility and value of AI should be demonstrated without making high investments.

Instead of relying on expensive company-wide investments, companies should use targeted and specialized tools (e.g., SaaS solutions). The infrastructure does not yet need to be scalable, but only needs to meet the requirements of the pilot projects. An open communication strategy is necessary to address employee concerns and highlight additional benefits. To this end, it is important to identify "AI champions" so that they can be used as advocates.

From maturity level 2 (fragmented) to 3 (established)

The focus in this phase is on standardization and strategic integration. Overcoming isolated applications is the biggest challenge and should be addressed with a coherent strategy. The pilot projects discussed above must be translated into a coherent, company-wide AI strategy. Responsibilities and roles must be defined (e.g., a Chief AI Officer). A formal governance structure must be established that covers guidelines for data access, use, and ethical aspects.

Data must be consolidated in central data platforms, such as data lakes or data warehouses. To ensure seamless integration between different systems, investment must be made in API

management. Active change management must be developed to support employees. Initially, company-wide training programs should be offered to increase general AI literacy and build the necessary skills.

From maturity level 3 (Established) to 4 (Systematic)

The goal of this transition is measurement and continuous improvement. Once companies have laid the groundwork, they must learn to quantify and manage the value created by AI. An AI strategy must be deeply embedded in day-to-day business. Key performance indicators (KPIs) should be defined to monitor the performance of AI-supported processes. Implementing performance management systems can make the successes of the AI initiative visible.

Data preparation and analysis must be automated. The use of process mining is recommended to identify process bottlenecks and further optimization opportunities. The use of predictive models is recommended and should lead to improved data-based decisions. A data-driven corporate culture must be promoted so that employees are encouraged to use AI results in their daily work. Communication aims to find continuous improvement in processes rather than relying on one-time success.

From maturity level 4 (Systematic) to 5 (Optimized)

The highest level implies a transformation of the business model. The goal is no longer just to gain efficiency, but to create new competitive advantages and business models. AI is positioned as a strategic lever for innovation. The task of senior management is to actively seek opportunities to transform existing business models through AI or to develop new ones.

At the highest level, the technical requirements are very high. AI systems must be able to adapt autonomously and independently. The infrastructure must support the processing and scaling of complex AI models in real time. Investments in research and development are necessary to adapt new AI technologies. Employees focus on creative and strategic tasks, while AI performs routine tasks autonomously. Hyperautomation is created, enabling the dynamic adaptation of processes to changing market conditions and collaboration between humans and machines.

4.3.2 Specific recommendations for overcoming identified obstacles

While Chapter 4.2.1 focused on general recommendations for action, this chapter deals with specific recommendations for the analysis of challenges carried out in Chapter 3. These recommendations are intended to help service companies proactively close the gap between the identified current state and the desired target state.

Overcoming organizational hurdles

The biggest problem is that most companies do not have a clear AI strategy, which leads to an underestimation of the full value creation potential of AI. It is the task of senior management to develop an adequate AI strategy that is directly linked to the company's goals. This strategy forms the

foundation for cooperation between the various departments. Management plays a crucial role here in providing the necessary vision and direction.

Successful implementation of AI requires a large budget for adoption opportunities (training, change management), which are usually more expensive than the technologies themselves. This is intended to reduce a "cold start" of AI models. It should be noted that the central organizational challenge lies not in the initial project, but in the company-wide expansion of the initiative. Therefore, a robust governance structure must be created for ethical use and to minimize the risk of data breaches and cybersecurity issues. The introduction of a Center of Excellence (CoE) or the use of a "hub-and-spoke" model for disseminating knowledge and responsibilities can help ensure scalability and governance. It is also necessary to prioritize projects according to their expected business value.

Overcoming technological hurdles

The performance of AI is severely hampered by two factors: inadequate data quality and the complexity of integration with existing legacy systems. To improve the performance of the AI model, data centralization must be prioritized. Structured, clean, and easily accessible data on a unified platform makes automation processes more efficient and reliable. This central database helps with the training and operation of powerful AI models. Experts point out that the fragmentation of data into silos is a hurdle that must be addressed and resolved.

Integration into the system landscape is another hurdle. There is a discrepancy between stable but inflexible legacy systems and the necessary flexible, modern AI systems. This is where the AI tech stack can be used. This approach improves collaboration between systems from different providers and helps to minimize vendor lock-in (dependence on a single provider). Furthermore, companies that are cloud-savvy have an easy start when it comes to introducing AI.

Due to increasing security concerns when handling sensitive information, technological risk management is essential. Clear guidelines must be established for the use of corporate AI tools in order to guarantee complete data security and meet compliance requirements. Experts recommend that initial explorations take place in a technically secure environment. In addition, every integrated component of AI projects should be subject to a risk impact assessment to ensure compliance with established cybersecurity standards.

Overcoming cultural barriers

A major hurdle to the integration of AI lies in corporate culture itself. Employees have concerns and fears about potential job losses and loss of control over their tasks. The expert interviews showed that middle management in particular fears loss of control. A targeted cultural initiative can reduce skepticism and increase acceptance.

To overcome fears and create new skills, "AI literacy" is necessary for all employees and managers. This means that a basic understanding of the functions and potential of AI must be created. It is

important here that no unrealistic expectations are created, which would view AI as "magic" and make its introduction more difficult. New skills should be taught through formal continuing education and training, such as an internal training program. This includes providing easy access to general-purpose AI so that employees can experience the opportunities in practice.

Transparent communication and proactive change management are essential for actively involving all employees in the change process. Managers must convey that AI improves the role and efficiency of employees and serves as a tool. This clear positioning promotes acceptance.

Another important aspect is the establishment of a learning culture that promotes a "test and learn" mentality and views mistakes as an important source of discovery and progress. In addition, employees should not feel bad about using AI, but rather demonstrate why and how they have used it. This attitude reduces the fear of failure and at the same time creates the basis for sustainable innovation in dealing with new technologies.

Overcoming legal and ethical hurdles

In the service sector in particular, the responsible handling of sensitive data and compliance with regulatory frameworks are of critical importance. Experts agree that compliance and security are fundamental requirements that must be addressed from the outset. Companies must ensure clear compliance and guarantee that data collection and use strictly adhere to the standards of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This applies explicitly because of the GDPR's principle of data minimization, which contrasts with the high data requirements of AI. For AI applications that pose a high risk, a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) can be useful to guarantee compliance with data protection regulations.

To guarantee the basic principles of transparency, fairness, and accountability, ethical guidelines and governance mechanisms must be implemented. These mechanisms help to actively check whether the AI system is biased. This is necessary to avoid discriminatory results against certain groups of people. As a concrete protective measure, companies apply the "human in the loop" (HITL) principle, whereby a human authority checks the results of automatic decisions made by AI in order to minimize legal vulnerability.

Companies should use the EU AI Act as a guide for the GDPR. This is particularly important to ensure that AI projects are not delayed by the current uncertainty surrounding the EU AI Act. This proactive approach makes it possible to ensure the security and ethical use of AI systems from the outset. In addition, future legal requirements can be addressed in advance before they become binding.

5 Exemplary model evaluation and derivation of specific recommendations for action for service companies

5.1 Selection and description of exemplary use cases/companies

The maturity model developed in Chapter 4 requires a final demonstration and evaluation phase as part of the design science research approach. The aim of this chapter is to demonstrate the practical applicability of the model in the German service sector through two application examples. The application examples do not represent a comprehensive analysis of the companies. They primarily serve as proof of concept. The focus is on the model and how it works to diagnose maturity gaps and derive targeted recommendations for action.

To illustrate the versatility of the model, two fictitious case studies from the German service sector have been constructed. These case studies are based on the key challenges identified in Chapter 3.

The case studies must cover different areas of the service sector and demonstrate different regulatory requirements and technological maturity. In addition, the two case studies will focus on different aspects of the five dimensions. The evaluation of the fictitious companies is based on the theoretical foundation of chapters 2 to 3.4 and links the practical experiences from the expert interviews in chapter 3.5. The fictitious companies are briefly presented below because the context is relevant for the later evaluation in chapter 5.2.

Case study 1: FDSE AG

FDSE AG is a large, traditional German insurance company based in Frankfurt. The company wants to use AI automation to reduce operating costs for mass processes (claims processing and document verification) and to improve compliance control. FDSE AG has an established IT infrastructure, but it is characterized by a strong legacy system.

Although top management has recognized the urgency of AI automation, projects are often delayed due to technological hurdles and high regulatory requirements. These include strict compliance with the GDPR and the demand for transparency in automated decisions. For this reason, FDSE AG will achieve a high level of maturity in the areas of law and ethics and processes (standardization), while technology and culture will be rated lower.

Case study 2: DigitalService GmbH

DigitalService GmbH is a medium-sized IT consulting company with a high affinity for technology. The motivation behind AI automation is to increase service quality and scalability in order to achieve a clear competitive advantage through new innovations. AI is to take over routine tasks in first-level service and project management.

Due to a lack of central governance and cultural resistance among employees, the company is struggling with the absence of a holistic automation strategy. DigitalService GmbH's maturity model is expected to show high maturity in the areas of data and technology, but low maturity in the areas of strategy & governance (lack of standardization) and culture & competence (change management).

5.2 Performing the model evaluation for the selected examples

This chapter deals with the systematic application of the maturity model, building on the case studies presented in Chapter 5.1. The implementation of the model forms the final demonstration phase of the design science research approach. It serves to demonstrate how the artifact works under realistic conditions.

The goal is to use the maturity model to represent the current state of AI maturity in the two case studies, FDSE and DigitalService. This is done by assigning a maturity level (level 1 to level 5) to each dimension. The indicator matrix is used as a checklist for each of the five dimensions. A check is made to see which of the criteria for the respective maturity level are met and which are not. Finally, the dominant maturity level is determined for each dimension. In case of uncertainty, the target description of the respective maturity level defined in Chapter 4 serves as the primary basis for evaluation.

First, both case studies are presented visually. Then the assessments are briefly explained, with a focus on the dimensions with the lowest maturity level. The textual explanation serves as a transition to the next chapter, in which specific recommendations are derived.

Maturity Profile FDSE AG: Current State after Model Assessment

Figure 2: Evaluation of FDSE AG based on the model (own representation)

The results for FDSE AG reveal an imbalance in the maturity model. FDSE AG achieves relatively high levels in the dimensions of Law & Ethics (Level 4 Systematic) and Processes & Automation (Level 3 Established). This reflects the need to act in accordance with strict regulatory requirements and high process standardization.

On the other hand, the Data and Technology dimension (Level 2 Fragmented) performs less well. This is due to isolated data structures and the existence of legacy systems. Culture and Competencies (Level 2 Fragmented) also scores low due to cultural resistance among the workforce, which fears a loss of control. The model diagnoses a compliance imbalance: excessive adherence to rules is slowing down implementation both technically and culturally.

Maturity Profile DigitalService GmbH: Current State after Model Assessment

Figure3: Evaluation of DigitalService GmbH based on the model (own representation)

The profile of DigitalService GmbH contrasts with that of FDSE AG. The dimensions of data and technology (level 4: systematic) and culture and competencies (level 4: systematic) show a high degree of maturity. The agile company has employees who are open to technology, and the technical infrastructure is flexible.

Nevertheless, there is a gap in the controlling dimensions. The strategy and governance dimension is only rated at level 2 (fragmented), as many individual projects are uncoordinated and there is no company-wide AI roadmap. There is a need for development in the legal and ethics dimension. The monitoring of algorithms and compliance with upcoming legislation (AI Act) is not yet fully integrated into the company's processes. The model identifies a scaling and governance problem here.

The different profiles of the two case studies prove that the model works. It provides a diagnosis that goes beyond technical evaluation. The identification of various discrepancies (e.g., FDSE AG with greater legal and ethical expertise than technological expertise, or DigitalService GmbH with a very

high affinity for technology and processes but weak governance) forms the basis for deriving specific recommendations for action in the next chapter.

5.3 Derivation of specific recommendations for action based on the model evaluation

Based on the results of the model evaluation in section 5.2 and the clear imbalances in the maturity models of the case studies, this section derives specific and tailored recommendations for action. The maturity model thus functions as a navigation tool and is now intended to close the identified gaps between the current state and the target state. The recommendations are based on best practices and critical solution approaches gained from the interviews.

1. Specific recommendations for FDSE AG (focus: technology and culture gap)

The objective of these recommendations is to remove internal barriers and create the technological basis for scaling, which is already in place thanks to the preparatory work carried out by the compliance department. To enable scaling, investments are needed to connect legacy systems and consolidate data using central platforms (data lake/warehouse). Experts describe data availability from legacy systems as one of the biggest hurdles. Without it, scaling AI models is not possible.

The process dimension is established, but before a process can be automated with regard to AI, it must undergo a binding review to determine whether it needs to be optimized (re-engineering). This prevents companies from "automating a bad process," which experts identify as a cause of failure.

Culturally, FDSE AG must establish a transparent communication strategy that positions the benefits of AI as "augmentation, not replacement" (helper). The targeted communication strategy addresses employee fears and middle management resistance to the feared loss of control and is therefore crucial for cultural acceptance.

2. Specific recommendations for DigitalService GmbH (focus: governance and scaling gap)

The recommendations must channel the energy of the agile teams and create a suitable governance structure, which will ensure sustainable scaling. Implementing a hub-and-spoke model can help overcome fragmented pilot projects. Technology affinity can be leveraged to establish a Center of Excellence (CoE) (hub). The CoE acts as a central point for defining standards and coordinating initiatives. Responsibility for the projects must be transferred to the relevant departments to ensure the sustainability of the investments.

Despite the affinity for technology, there is room for improvement in dealing with legal decisions. Establishing an AI governance framework and using the Human in the Loop (HITL) principle can help to achieve a higher level in the legal and ethical dimension. This is particularly important to ensure compliance with the EU AI Act and minimize liability risks.

To achieve improvement in the dimension of processes and automation, high technological maturity can help ensure that the transformation of core processes leads to value creation. Reaching level 3

is characterized by the ability not only to automate processes, but also to fundamentally redesign them through end-to-end re-engineering.

This section concludes that the maturity model provides direct and practical guidance for further developing AI maturity through its dimension-specific approach. It shows that it is not necessarily necessary to invest in cost-intensive general strategies. Instead, companies can use their scarce resources to identify their weaknesses, which accelerates the transformation.

6 Reflection on the applicability and practicality of the model

The concluding chapter summarizes the findings of this bachelor thesis by answering the research questions. In addition, the scientific contribution, the practical benefits for the German service industry, and the limitations of the thesis are presented, and an outlook for future research is provided.

6.1 Answering the research question(s)

Key research question: What dimensions and stages does a practice-oriented maturity model encompass that systematically controls the implementation of AI for process automation in the German service industry?

The finished artifact, the maturity model for AI implementation for process automation in the German service industry, comprises five dimensions and five maturity levels. With the help of the model, companies can navigate from level 1 (initial) to level 5 (optimized).

The five dimensions of the maturity model

- **Strategy & Governance:** The focus is on establishing control mechanisms (e.g., CoE, hub-and-spoke model) and integrating a company-wide AI strategy.
- **Data & Technology:** The basis for an AI system consists of a robust, scalable data infrastructure, effective data quality management, and seamless system integration (including legacy systems).
- **Processes & Automation:** Evaluation of the depth and breadth of AI usage, starting with rule-based automation and extending to advanced end-to-end re-engineering automation.
- **Culture & skills:** Consideration of human factors, including employee acceptance, targeted change management, promotion of AI literacy, and establishment of a "test and learn" mentality.
- **Law & Ethics:** Ensuring compliance with regulatory frameworks (GDPR, EU AI Act) and guaranteeing fairness, transparency, and responsibility (e.g., through the "human in the loop" (HITL) principle).

Research question 1: What organizational, technological, cultural, legal, and ethical challenges are dominant in the implementation of AI for process automation in the German service industry?

The study identified several challenges that can be divided into four different dimensions and were confirmed by the expert interviews:

- Organizational: A major challenge is the scalability of pilot projects and the lack of a clear corporate strategy linked to AI. In addition, insufficient funding for adoption measures is a risk factor.
- Technological: The fragmentation of data into silos and the lack of data quality pose a major technical problem. Added to this is the complexity of integration with rigid legacy systems and growing concerns about cybersecurity.
- Cultural: Despite low fears of job loss, the main hurdle lies with middle management and the associated loss of control. In addition, unrealistic expectation management (AI is magic) and the lack of company-wide "AI literacy" are problematic.
- Legal and ethical: Regulatory uncertainty caused by the EU AI Act is delaying projects. Increased demand for explainability (XAI) and more complex compliance requirements (GDPR, avoidance of bias) are legal and ethical challenges that need to be addressed.

Research question 2: How can the theoretical concepts of maturity models be transferred to AI implementation, and which dimensions and stages need to be taken into account?

A novel model was developed using design science research (DSR). This model transfers the logical principles of the maturity model (actual state analysis, target state definition, and step-by-step progression) to the implementation of AI. The analysis of existing models has revealed a research gap with regard to the specific focus on AI-supported process automation in the German service sector, with explicit consideration of the legal and ethical dimensions. This identified gap was closed by the five dimensions mentioned above and the detailed elaboration of five maturity levels.

Research question 3: How can the developed maturity model be applied in an exemplary manner to assess the current status of a company and derive concrete recommendations for action for the next maturity level?

The exemplary application of the model was demonstrated in two case studies (FDSE AG and DigitalService GmbH) in Chapter 5. The model enables a dimension-specific diagnosis of digital maturity and can identify an imbalance (FDSE AG: high legal maturity, low technical/cultural maturity) and a governance and scaling problem (DigitalService GmbH: high technical/cultural maturity, low strategic/legal maturity). Based on the diagnosis, various recommendations for action were derived for different scenarios (e.g., investment in data consolidation at FDSE AG; implementation of a

CoE/hub-and-spoke model at DigitalService GmbH), which serve as a concrete roadmap for closing the identified gaps.

6.2 Scientific contribution of the work

The scientific contribution of this work is the development of a holistic maturity model that is explicitly tailored to the strategic implementation of AI for process automation in the German service sector. This model closes the existing gaps in the specialist literature.

The work achieves this through three key points:

- The model combines a technology and process approach by integrating AI, Intelligent Process Automation (IPA), and end-to-end re-engineering.
- The foundation of the methodology was confirmed by the DSR (Design Science Research) approach and the empirical validation of the dimensions through expert interviews.
- The integration of the dimension of law and ethics serves to address the specific requirements of the highly regulated German service sector with regard to the GDPR and the EU AI Act.

6.3 Practical benefits and implications for the service industry

The model offers German companies direct practical benefits by enabling them to use the tool to reduce complexity and prioritize strategies. These benefits manifest themselves in three ways:

- Systematic assessment of current status: Managers have the opportunity to objectively evaluate the current level of AI maturity across all areas of the company. The spider web diagram makes strengths and weaknesses visible at a glance, which helps to create a clear basis for discussion.
- Focused investment decisions: The model makes it possible to identify gaps and address them as planned. This helps to use scarce resources more effectively. To this end, precise recommendations for action can be used, such as prioritizing the elimination of data silos as a necessary foundation before scaling further AI initiatives.
- Interdisciplinary communication basis: The model helps create a shared vision. From the relevant stakeholders to senior management to the IT and compliance departments. This promotes acceptance and the coordinated rollout of the AI initiative throughout the company.

6.4 Limitations of the study and outlook for future research

Although the maturity model developed provides a solid basis for the strategic implementation of AI in the German service sector, the work is subject to the following limitations:

Firstly, the model was only applied to fictitious companies, which limited the full validation of its practical applicability. Second, the empirical basis is limited by the small sample size, as the number of 3 expert interviews cannot be considered representative. Third, the rapid development of AI

technology, especially in the field of GenAI, requires continuous updating of the model to ensure its long-term relevance.

These limitations give rise to the following approaches for future research:

- Comprehensive validation: In the future, a qualitative study could be conducted, for example, a large-scale survey in the German service industry, to comprehensively validate and weight the defined dimensions and indicators of the model.
- Development of a set of metrics: The model should be supplemented with clear, quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) for each maturity level (e.g., "time to value" of AI projects) so that the qualitative self-assessment is underpinned by hard data.
- Specific GenKI focus: Current technological developments show that the model needs to be expanded to address specific challenges in the implementation and governance of large language models (LLMs).

Bibliography

- Aalst, W. van der. (2016). *Process mining [electronic resource]: Data science in action* (iuo.oai.edge.iu.folio.ebsco.com.fs00001148.d3766fdb.87e4.5326.a922.d841375fc33a; Second edition). Springer. <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=957c60d6-38db-354b-a51b-31e20d6fd982>
- Alex, S., & Robra-Bissantz, S. (2024). Implementierung von 360-Grad-Personas auf Basis von Action Design Research und Design Science Research – Ein Forschungsprojekt mit der Praxis. *HMD Praxis der Wirtschaftsinformatik*, 61(3), 802–819. <https://doi.org/10.1365/s40702-023-01024-5>
- Altenfelder, K., Kieffer-Radwan, S., & Schönfeld, D. (Hrsg.). (2025). *Services Management und Künstliche Intelligenz: Grundlagen und Anwendungsfelder für den Einsatz von KI-unterstützten Services*. Springer Fachmedien. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-46665-7>
- Anica-Popa, L.-E., Vrîncianu, M., & Petrică Papuc, I.-M. (2023). AI – powered Business Services in the Hyperautomation Era. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*, 17(1), 1036–1050. <https://doi.org/10.2478/picbe-2023-0094>
- Barenkamp, M. (2025). *Wertschöpfung durch KI: Chancen für Unternehmen und Gesellschaft*. Springer Fachmedien. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-47482-9>
- Barenkamp, M., & Schnier, T. (2023). Künstliche Intelligenz im Process Mining – Anwendung und Potenziale. *Wirtschaftsinformatik & Management*, 15(2), 134–140. <https://doi.org/10.1365/s35764-023-00468-0>
- Bartoletti, I., Chishti, S., Leslie, A., & Millie, S. M. (2020). *The AI book: The artificial intelligence handbook for investors, entrepreneurs and fintech visionaries* (edsvle.AH36662015). John Wiley & Sons, Inc. <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=acf6404e-4ac8-3f4b-9f9d-9fc380046cf0>
- Blanco, J. L., Parsons, M., Fuchs, S., & Ribeirinho, M. J. (2018). Artificial intelligence: Construction technology's next frontier. *McKinsey Insights*, 1–1.
- Bolwin, L., Dr.Hönig, T., Kempermann, C., Dr. Klink, H., Kuttler, F., & Prof. Dr. van Baal, S. (2023). *Der digitale Faktor: Wie Deutschland von intelligenten Technologien profitiert*. Google.

- Breiter, K., Lohmann, T., Stahl, B., Zilmans, C., Reischl-Lenz, B., & Gimpel, H. (2025). Generative KI in der Finanzbranche: Strategische, technologische und organisationale Implementierung am Beispiel der DZ BANK AG. *HMD Praxis der Wirtschaftsinformatik*, 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.1365/s40702-025-01166-8>
- Bruhn, M., & Hadwich, K. (2023). *Künstliche Intelligenz im Dienstleistungsmanagement Band 2, Einsatzfelder – Akzeptanz – Kundeninteraktionen* (edshbz.99373312395906441). Springer Gabler. <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=16ed41e2-8627-39c1-be9c-32e47bff075d>
- Brynjolfsson, E., & McAfee, A. (2014). *The second machine age [electronic resource]: Work, progress, and prosperity in a time of brilliant technologies* (iuo.oai.edge.iu.folio.ebsco.com.fs00001148.794ee68b.8ef9.51b8.9bee.5fff59fec205; 1. ed.). W.W. Norton & Company. <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=295fe3d4-5374-32d1-989f-df551b2e202e>
- Bulander, R., Kreuzwieser, S., Kimmig, A., Kölmel, B., & Ovtcharova, J. (2022). Robotic Process Automation und Künstliche Intelligenz. *ERP Management*, 18(4), 44–49.
https://doi.org/10.30844/erp_22-4_44-49
- Busik, V. (2024). Wie künstliche Intelligenz und Large Language Models die Dermatologie revolutionieren. *Die Dermatologie*, 75(9), 743–746. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00105-024-05379-8>
- Chatterjee, S., Sundarraj, R. P., & Dutta, K. (2023). Editorial Special Issue: Design Science Research in Information Systems and Technology. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management, Engineering Management, IEEE Transactions on, IEEE Trans. Eng. Manage.*, 70(3), 803–805. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2023.3235644>
- Dahm, M. H., & Schulz, B. (2024). *Künstliche Intelligenz im Consulting: Handlungsempfehlungen und Zukunftsprognosen für Unternehmensberater*. Springer Fachmedien.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-45060-1>
- Enholm, I. M., Papagiannidis, E., Mikalef, P., & Krogstie, J. (2022). Artificial Intelligence and Business Value: A Literature Review. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 24(5), 1709–1734.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-021-10186-w>

- Fontaine, T., McCarthy, B., & Saleh, T. (2021). Building the AI-Powered Organization. *Harvard Business Review*, 10–19.
- Fronczek, S., Graf-Pfohl, C., Böhme, C., & Andersen, G. (2024). KI-Implementierung im Unternehmen: Ein Managementkonzept. *Zeitschrift Führung und Organisation*, 93(4), 212–218. <https://doi.org/10.34156/0722-7485-2024-4-212>
- Gentsch, P. (2018). *Künstliche Intelligenz für Sales, Marketing und Service*. Springer Fachmedien. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-19147-4>
- Gökalp, E., & Martinez, V. (2022). Digital transformation maturity assessment: Development of the digital transformation capability maturity model. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(20), 6282–6302. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2021.1991020>
- Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y., & Courville, A. (2016). *Deep Learning*. The MIT Press. <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=138987f9-5609-3627-b1b1-7786845e21e2>
- Haller, S., & Wissing, C. (2022). Bedeutung und Merkmale von Dienstleistungen. In S. Haller & C. Wissing (Hrsg.), *Dienstleistungsmanagement: Grundlagen – Konzepte – Instrumente* (S. 1–37). Springer Fachmedien. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-36810-4_1
- Hecker, J., & Czachowski, L. (2024). *Künstliche Intelligenz in Deutschland: Perspektiven aus Bevölkerung & Unternehmen (KI & Daten)*. bitkom e.V.
- Heinrichs, C. (2024). KI in der Automatisierung: Effizienz ja, Strategie nein?: Ergebnisse der Studie „Intelligent Process Automation 2024“. *IM + io*, 4, 32–35.
- Hevner, A. R., March, S. T., Park, J., & Ram, S. (2004). DESIGN SCIENCE IN INFORMATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH. *MIS Quarterly*, 28(1), 75–105. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25148625>
- Hochkamp, F., Scheidler, A. A., & Rabe, M. (2025). Review of Maturity Models for Data Mining and Proposal of a Data Preparation Maturity Model Prototype for Data Mining. *Computers (2073-431X)*, 14(4), 146. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers14040146>
- Humble, N., & Mozelius, P. (2023). Design science for Small Scale Studies: Recommendations for Undergraduates and Junior Researchers. *Proceedings of the European Conference on Research Methods for Business & Management Studies*, 87–92. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecrm.22.1.1702>

- Hüsch, A., Distelrath, D., & Hüsch, T. (2023). *Einsatzmöglichkeiten von GPT in Finance, Compliance und Audit: Vorteile, Herausforderungen, Praxisbeispiele*. Springer Fachmedien.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-41419-1>
- Iansiti, M., & Lakhani, K. R. (2020). *COMPETING in THE AGE of AI*. (140216540; Bd. 98). Harvard University. <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=98f514d2-8871-3df2-8dad-2e918deaf9c5>
- Kaplan, A., & Haenlein, M. (2019). Siri, Siri, in my hand: Who's the fairest in the land? On the interpretations, illustrations, and implications of artificial intelligence. *Business Horizons ; Volume 62, Issue 1, Page 15-25; ISSN 0007-6813*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2018.08.004>
- Limat, C. (2022). Disruptionspotenzial künstlicher Intelligenz: Ein Reifegradmodell zur Einführung ganzheitlicher KI-Initiativen in Unternehmen. *Wirtschaftsinformatik & Management, 14(1)*, 60–67. <https://doi.org/10.1365/s35764-021-00379-y>
- Mangiapane, M., & Büchler, R. P. (2024). *Modernes IT-Management: Methodische Kombination von IT-Strategie und IT-Reifegradmodell* (2. Auflage). Springer Vieweg.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-43317-8>
- Noymanee, J., Iewwongcharoen, B., & Theeramunkong, T. (2022). Artificial Intelligence Maturity Model for Government Administration and Service. *2022 International Conference on Digital Government Technology and Innovation (DGTi-CON), Digital Government Technology and Innovation (DGTi-CON), 2022 International Conference on*, 66–70.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/DGTi-CON53875.2022.9849184>
- Omol, E. J., Mburu, L. W., & Abuonji, P. A. (2025). Digital Maturity Assessment Model (DMAM): Assimilation of Design Science Research (DSR) and Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI). *Digital Transformation and Society, 4(2)*, 128–152. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DTS-04-2024-0049>
- Raiser do Ó, M. (2024). Digitale Transformation: Automatisieren, aber richtig: Prozessautomatisierung, Datenzentralisierung und Anwendungskonsolidierung senken die Kosten und eröffnen neue Wachstumschancen. *Rethinking Finance, 2*, 12–17.

- Ramdhani, Y. L., & Surendro, K. (2022). Development of AI Governance Model in Enterprises Based on CMMI Model Structure. *2022 International Conference on Information Technology Systems and Innovation (ICITSI), Information Technology Systems and Innovation (ICITSI), 2022 International Conference on*, 145–150.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICITSI56531.2022.9970981>
- Renner, D., Reicher, D., & Vancea, C. (2025). *KI im Mittelstand: Chancen, Optimierungen und Neugeschäft*. Springer Fachmedien. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-46077-8>
- Russell, S. J. (2021). *Artificial intelligence: A modern approach* (edsvle.AH39026756). Pearson.
<https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=7bbb4500-62ba-350b-a732-7a3568e1d04e>
- Sarstedt, M., & Wecke, B. (2022). *Skalierung von KI im Marketing und die neue Rolle des CMO*. Springer Fachmedien. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-37864-6>
- Schneider, P. (2024). Eine Typologie praktischer Anwendungsfälle generativer KI. *IM + io*, 3, 38–41.
- Shang, ShariS. C., & Lin, S.-F. (2009). Understanding the effectiveness of Capability Maturity Model Integration by examining the knowledge. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 20(5), 509–521. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783360902863671>
- Shum, H. H. (2023). Utilising Generative AI in Businesses: Risks and Best Practices. *Business Law International*, 24(3), 215–232.
- Thomas, F. (2024, Oktober 1). Barriers to AI Adoption. *Pharmaceutical Technology Europe*, 36(9).
<https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=db945d92-4d0d-3597-b94c-e89adbdd7087>
- Thordsen, T., & Bick, M. (2023). A decade of digital maturity models: Much ado about nothing? *Information Systems & E-Business Management*, 21(4), 947–976.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10257-023-00656-w>
- Tsaih, R.-H., Chang, H.-L., Hsu, C.-C., & Yen, D. C. (2023). The AI Tech-Stack Model: Management and technology challenges of AI-enabled application projects. *Communications of the ACM*, 66(3), 69–77. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3568026>

- Vayena, E., Jobin, A., & Ienca, M. (2019). The global landscape of AI ethics guidelines. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 1, 389–399. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0088-2>
- Veale, M., & Binns, R. (2017). Fairer machine learning in the real world: Mitigating discrimination without collecting sensitive data. *Big Data & Society*, 4 (2) Pp. 1-17. (2017. <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=e4d875e5-438f-3e78-bfe1-e0ca02d51b33>
- Weigand, H., & Johannesson, P. (2023). How to Identify your Design Science Research Artifact. *2023 IEEE 25th Conference on Business Informatics (CBI), Business Informatics (CBI), 2023 IEEE 25th Conference on*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBI58679.2023.10187511>
- Westerman, G., Bonnet, D., & McAfee, A. (2014). *Leading Digital [electronic resource]: Turning Technology into Business Transformation* (iuo.oai.edge.iu.folio.ebsco.com.fs00001148.3fb2e6d5.c16b.594f.b0d8.5997aa23aa63; 1. Aufl.). Harvard Business Review Press. <https://research.ebsco.com/linkprocessor/plink?id=71701049-2e96-3987-a0aa-239b659dfa23>
- Wisbey1, O. (o. J.). *Was generative KI und Large Language Models unterscheidet* | *Computer Weekly*. ComputerWeekly.de. Abgerufen 9. Juli 2025, von <https://www.computer-weekly.com/de/tipp/Was-generative-KI-und-Large-Language-Models-unterscheidet>
- Wüst, J. (2025). Vom Experiment zum Erfolgsmodell: Wie Finanzinstitute generative KI richtig skalieren. *Harvard Business Manager*, 2, 4–4.

Appendix with list

Appendix 1 Interview guide

Interview guide for exploratory expert interviews

Topic of the bachelor thesis: Development of a maturity model for managing AI implementation for process automation in the German service industry: A synthesis of literature analysis and exploratory expert interviews with exemplary model evaluation and recommendations for action.

Aim of the interview: To gain practical perspectives and concrete insights into the challenges and initial approaches to implementing AI for process automation in the German service industry. The findings will serve as input for the development of a maturity model.

Estimated duration: 25-35 minutes

Introduction to the interview (by interviewer)

- "Dear Mr./Ms. [name of interviewee],
- Thank you very much for taking the time to talk to me today. My name is [your name], and I am studying digital business at IU International University."
- "As part of my bachelor's thesis, I am working on the development of a maturity model for managing AI implementation for process automation in the German service industry."
- "The aim of this interview is to benefit from your valuable practical experience. I would like to gain your perspective on the current challenges and initial approaches to solutions in the introduction of AI for process automation. Your insights are an important input for my model."
- "The interview is expected to take 25-35 minutes. Your answers will of course be anonymized and treated confidentially so that no conclusions can be drawn about you or your company. The results will be used exclusively for this scientific work."
- "Would you agree to the interview being audio recorded for my internal note-taking purposes? [If applicable, present/send consent form for signature]."

Main part of the interview guide

A. General classification & role of AI/automation in the company (Context)

- What role does digitalization play in your company's day-to-day business in general?
- Can you briefly describe your company's position/role in the service sector and your own function in relation to digitalization/AI?
- What strategic importance does the use of artificial intelligence, and process automation in particular, have for your company at present and in the next 3-5 years?
- In which areas or for which processes do you currently see the greatest potential for AI-supported automation in your company or industry? Can you give specific examples?

B. Specific challenges of AI implementation

1. Organizational aspects (strategy, processes, resources)

- What strategic or structural hurdles do you encounter when implementing AI for process automation?
 - Possible follow-up questions: Do you have difficulties with a clear AI strategy, unclear responsibilities, or a lack of resources?
- How do you deal with existing processes needing to be adapted or new roles and skills becoming necessary as a result of AI automation?

2. Technological aspects (data, integration, scaling, security)

- Which technological hurdles are most relevant when introducing AI automation solutions in your company?
 - Possible follow-up questions: Are issues such as data quality, integration with legacy systems, or scaling pilot projects relevant?
- What role do cybersecurity and IT risk management play in the planning and implementation of your AI automation projects?

3. Cultural aspects & employee acceptance (fears, skills, change management)

- What impact does AI automation have on your employees, and what concerns or resistance do you perceive here?
 - Possible follow-up questions: Are there concerns such as fear of job loss or lack of trust in AI systems?
- What measures are you taking to promote employee acceptance and build the necessary skills for working with AI?

4. Legal & Ethical Aspects (Data Protection, Compliance, Transparency)

- What role do data protection (e.g., GDPR) and other legal frameworks (e.g., AI Act) play in your AI automation projects? What challenges do they pose?
- How does your company address ethical issues such as the transparency of AI decisions or the fairness of algorithms? Are there internal guidelines or fixed structures in place?

C. Approaches & Recommendations (Input for Model & Recommendations for Action)

- Based on your experience: Which of the challenges mentioned proved to be the most critical or difficult to overcome?
- Can you share best practices or lessons learned from your previous AI automation projects that helped you overcome these hurdles?

- Follow-up question: Can you give a specific example of how this was implemented in your company?
- What advice would you give to a service company that is just starting to implement AI?
- Could you imagine a multi-stage model that guides companies through these steps? If so, which stages or phases would be most important to you?

Conclusion of the interview (by interviewer)

"Thank you very much for your time and the extremely valuable insights, Mr./Ms. [name of interview partner]. Your perspectives are a great asset to my bachelor's thesis. Is there anything else you would like to add, or a question I haven't asked that you think is important? I wish you continued success with your projects!"

Anhang 2

Table 3: Practical indicators Table for assessing current maturity (own representation)

Maturity Level	Strategy & Governance	Data & Technology	Processes & Automation	Culture & Competencies	Law & Ethics
Level 1: Initial	Is the implementation of AI systems driven exclusively by individual employees or departments? (Yes/No)	Is the data for automation available in different, unconnected systems? (Yes/No)	Are processes automated manually or only through simple, rule-based scripts that do not use AI? (Yes/No)	Is there open skepticism or fear among employees regarding AI and its impact on their roles? (Yes/No)	Do no clear internal guidelines exist for dealing with AI tools? (Yes/No)
Level 2: Fragmented	Were initial AI pilot projects with limited scope started in individual departments? (Yes/No)	Is data manually extracted and prepared for use by the AI for pilot projects? (Yes/No)	Are AI solutions only tested in non-critical sub-processes, such as email sorting? (Yes/No)	Have initial informal "AI champions" formed who drive the technology forward within the team? (Yes/No)	Are data protection and compliance issues only handled ad-hoc and project-specific? (Yes/No)
Level 3: Established	Does a formally documented and communicated AI strategy exist, which is supported by the management? (Yes/No)	Is data from all relevant departments collected in a central, company-wide platform (Data Lake/Warehouse)? (Yes/No)	Are AI applications integrated into core processes and demonstrably contribute to value creation? (Yes/No)	Is there structured change management and formal training to promote the AI competence of the employees? (Yes/No)	Are ethical guidelines for AI anchored in corporate governance and checked before project start? (Yes/No)
Level 4: Systematic	Is the performance of AI projects systematically measured and monitored using quantitative KPIs? (Yes/No)	Are data quality and the correctness of the algorithms (e.g., for bias) regularly checked by automated tools? (Yes/No)	Are AI-supported processes found that enable predictive analyses and self-optimization? (Yes/No)	Is the "Test-and-Learn" mentality in dealing with new technologies firmly anchored in the corporate culture? (Yes/No)	Are the AI systems regularly audited with regard to compliance with the EU AI Act and the GDPR? (Yes/No)
Level 5: Optimized	Does AI automation serve as the primary driver for the development of new services or business models? (Yes/No)	Are predictive analyses used for real-time control of business processes? (Yes/No)	Is active hyper-automation taking place that enables dynamic and autonomous process adaptation? (Yes/No)	Is AI competence deeply anchored throughout the corporate culture and considered a strategic advantage? (Yes/No)	Does the company take on a pioneering role and set industry standards for ethically responsible AI use? (Yes/No)

Anhang C: Eidesstattliche Erklärung

Hiermit versichere ich an Eides statt, dass ich die Abschlussarbeit selbständig und ohne Inanspruchnahme fremder Hilfe angefertigt habe. Ich habe dabei nur die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel verwendet und die aus diesen wörtlich oder inhaltlich entnommenen Stellen als solche kenntlich gemacht. Die Arbeit hat in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form noch keiner anderen Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegen. Ich erkläre mich damit einverstanden, dass die Arbeit mit Hilfe eines Plagiatserkennungsdienstes auf enthaltene Plagiate überprüft wird.

